

D6.2: FLW Capacity Building

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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
CBA	Capacity Building Activity
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
PO	Producer Organization
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
STH	Semantic Tree House
SIRL	Systemic Innovation Readiness Level

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the capacity building activities (CBAs) organized within the ZeroW project, a core component of Task 6.2 (T6.2) aimed at enhancing actors' and consumers' capacities to leverage Food Loss and Waste (FLW) innovations. The ultimate goal of these activities was to support the systemic innovations developed in the Systemic Innovations Living Labs (SILLs) in their journey towards near-zero FLW. The selection and preparation of these CBAs was a meticulous process. The aim was to organize at least three activities in each of the three macro-regions, ideally one activity per SILL. This selection was guided by several key criteria:

- SIRL reports from D5.3 were utilized to identify specific bottleneck dimensions within the systemic innovations that required targeted support.
- Lessons learned from stakeholder workshops reported in D6.1 provided insights into critical barriers, helping to prioritize suitable topics for CBAs.
- An evaluation of SILLs through a systems and product innovation lens helped understand their unique "why, what, and how".
- Consideration was given to the preferred scaling strategies for solutions: "scaling up" (expanding within a sector), "scaling out" (replicating in new contexts), or "scaling deep" (impacting cultural roots).
- Practical considerations such as the usefulness of a CBA for multiple SILLs, available resources, geographical spread, and synergies with other project tasks were also factored in.

This led to an initial longlist of 37 potential activities, which was further refined and finalized in consultation with SILL coordinators. The chosen CBAs were diverse, ranging from technical workshops, expert panels, and study trips to policy-focused workshops and open-sourcing initiatives. Each activity was specifically designed to address identified challenges and opportunities within individual SILLs, thereby fostering their implementation, adaptation, and upscaling. The deliverable provides a detailed account of the execution and outcomes of these CBAs.

The CBAs successfully enhanced a diverse set of capacities - including technical skills, organizational change management, systemic innovation approaches, and policy navigation. This strategic capacity building served as a critical bridge, enabling the technological advancements of the SILLs to translate into tangible, real-world impacts on food waste reduction and overall sustainability. The insights gained and capacities built are crucial for the continued scaling and impact of ZeroW's innovations beyond the project's lifetime.

1. Introduction

1.1. ZeroW project summary

ZeroW aims at reducing Food Loss and Waste by employing systemic innovations, to halve by 2030 and to near-zero by 2050. This systemic innovation approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (0FLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system.

Figure 1. ZeroW at a glance

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2. ZeroW approach

To reach its goals ZeroW is divided into 11 WPs with different goals, tasks and deliverables.

This deliverable reports on WP6 work, which aims to foster the systemic innovations that are built in the SILLs, by building capacities towards near-zero FLW. Importantly, WP6 aims to support T4.3 (Systemic innovation management and evolution in the SILLs) by organising concrete workshops and other types of activities.

Figure 3. WP6 tasks, deliverables, objectives, and link with other WPs

1.2. Mapping ZeroW outputs

Purpose of this chapter is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document.

Table 2 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D6.2 FLW Capacity Building</i>	FLW capacity building will present activities, materials & tools for appropriating value from FLW innovations	Chapters two, three and four	Chapter two explains how the capacity building activities were selected. Chapter three gives a description of the planned capacity building activities including the tools and methods that were used. Chapter four will report on how these were implemented and what lessons were learned from this process.
TASKS			
<i>T6.2 Enhancing actors' and consumers' capacity in appropriating</i>	To enhance actors' and consumers' capacity, this Task will focus on organising capacity building activities. Based on T6.1 and thus information on possible incentives and systemic innovation potential, a set of activities will be organised in the 3 macro regions, to further implement, adapt and	Chapters three and four	We will develop and execute minimal 9 capacity building activities. To ensure geographical spreading we will organise minimal one activity per SILL. The capacity building activities must support the scaling of the innovations in a broad societal point of view, beyond the lifetime of the project.

<p>value from FLW innovations</p>	<p>thus upscale systemic innovations from the SILLs. Each macro region will organise at least 3 activities (combination of online and physical activities) and will focus on enhancing a diverse set of capacities (technical skills, organisational change, systemic innovation approaches, coordination, monitoring, policy, etc.).</p>		
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Table 3 Distinction between ZeroW T4.5, T6.2 and T6.3

<p>T4.5 Post-project SILL sustainability/ funding strategies</p>	<p>T6.2 Enhancing actors' & consumers' capacity in appropriating value from FLW innovations</p>	<p>T6.3 Build-up regional scaling strategies to stimulate investment in FLW reduction by private and public actors</p>
<p>Based on SILL work within the project and linked to other WP's work</p>	<p>Looking outside the project and SILL boundaries</p>	<p>'serve' the SILLs</p>
<p>Provide SILLs solutions plans for moving from current TRL to TRL9 after project completion</p>	<p>Provide context to SILL bottlenecks/ opportunities</p>	<p>support SILLs in tackling bottlenecks/ grasping opportunities</p>

<p>Identify the SILLs strategic stakeholders that will impact the successful implementation of their solutions</p>	<p>Identify broader societal benefits, organise trainings, activities, materials that involve or are open/available for external parties</p>	<p>Identify investors, train SILLs on how to approach them effectively</p>
<p>Support SILLs with the SILLs Business plans and “Growth trajectories” for the SILLs that do not have commercial ambitions. Support SILLs with the individual SILL scaling up approach and funding strategy through explanation the governance models and self-sustainability of the organisational structure. Discussing in summary about the regulatory barriers and the findings of the SILLs in that direction</p>	<p>Support the SILLs partners and other stakeholders in building various capacities that enable scale-up (in)directly (e.g. <i>technical skills, organisational change, systemic innovation approaches, coordination, monitoring, policy, etc.</i>)</p>	<p>Support SILLs core partners in how to build their story, how to present their innovation to sell it or attract investors, and how to build regional scaling strategies to achieve scale-up in the real world</p>
<p>Approach: This deliverable is based on various work of WP4 and other ZeroW WPs. <i>(Input from D4.3 is used for developing SILL's strategic goals and objectives and Key stakeholders' section; input from D6.3 on SILL's financial strategies and D7.3 on SILL's Business plan/Growth trajectory is used for financial sustainability section; input from D2.3 on SILL's governance models is used for developing operational continuity section; input from D6.2</i></p>	<p>Approach: different capacity building activities (including workshops, targeted meetings, networking events, company visits, reports on literature research) were organised to enhance a set of diverse capabilities across various stakeholders towards a near-zero FLW system.</p>	<p>Approach: probably distinguish between private and public investors. The latter are governments, policy oriented, where distinction between regions is needed because of various contexts. the first are more commercial.</p>

on Capacity building activities is used for developing capacity building section and finally, input from WP8 on Policy barriers and policy actions is used for developing policy and advocacy section of Deliverable D4.5)

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The capacity building activities within the ZeroW project were designed to enhance the impact of technological innovations by addressing specific challenges related to their implementation, adoption, and scaling across different stages of the food supply chain. These activities aimed to support in overcoming bottlenecks and leveraging opportunities for their systemic solutions. The aim was to organise at least three activities in each of the three macro-regions, preferably 1 activity per SILL. **Chapter 2** outlines the multi-criteria process for selecting activities and preparing the nine capacity building activities (CBAs) for the ZeroW project, emphasising their dual purpose: implementing and upscaling SILL innovations and enhancing various capacities of actors. Consultation with the SILLs was central to ensure that the activities, tools and materials supported scaling strategies in the different regions. Additionally, findings from T6.1 on success factors and key incentives for scaling informed the purposes, scope, approaches and design of the CBAs. Altogether, the CBAs aimed to enhance a diverse set of capacities, ranging from technical skills to organisational change, tuned to the needs of various actors in various regions in order to reduce FLW through systemic innovations. **Chapter 3** provides the tangible details of each CBA: who was involved, when and where it took place, and what the immediate results and outcomes were. It offers concrete examples of how capacity was built, and innovation impact was supported. **Chapter 4** aims to draw general conclusions on organising capacity building activities in general and reflects on the impacts of the ZeroW CBAs. Altogether, the CBAs enhanced a diverse set of capacities, ranging from technical skills to organisational change, tuned to the needs of various actors in various regions in order to reduce FLW through systemic innovations. To ensure readability, detailed reports and participant lists are included in annexes rather than integrated in the report. Recordings and additional workshop materials are all available upon request.

2. Selection and preparation of capacity building activities

2.1. Developing a list of potential capacity building activities

To enhance actors' and consumers' capacity in appropriating value from FLW innovations, Task 6.2 organised 9 capacity building activities (CBAs) – 3 in each macro region. Some CBAs happened online, some physical, depending on the target audience and purpose of the CBA. The purpose of the CBAs was twofold: (1) to further implement, adapt and thus upscale systemic innovations from the SILLs; and (2) to enhance a diverse set of capacities (technical skills, organisational change, systemic innovation approaches, coordination, monitoring, policy, etc.) that actors need to benefit from or widen the benefits from FLW innovations. The process of

deciding what kind of CBAs would have high potential to enhance actors' and consumers' capacity took into account multiple criteria, as described hereafter.

First, T6.2 used the Systemic Innovation Readiness Level (SIRL) reports from D5.3 to understand systemic innovation potential and to determine which dimensions are bottleneck dimensions and hence require more support to develop. At the start of T6.2, the most recent SIRL data was from round 1, at which point many SILLs have several underdeveloped dimensions.

Second, based on the stakeholder workshops from T6.1 we obtained information on possible barriers and opportunities. Barriers identified as critical during the stakeholder workshops were deemed suitable topics for CBAs. These findings were complementary to the SIRL evaluations and helped prioritising the innovation dimensions in need of capacity building.

Third, we evaluated the SILLs with a systems and product innovation lens to understand their why, what, and how as well as the preferred way of scaling. The results of this evaluation are presented in [Table 4](#).

Fourth, and following from the previous criteria, WP6 partners reflected together with the SILLs whether certain aspects of their systemic solution would need to be scaled up, scaled out, or scaled deep and what such scaling would mean for their solution. With the final selection of the CBA's, we also tried to reach diversity in supporting those 3 types of scaling.

Lastly, some practical considerations were taken into account, such as the usefulness of a CBA for multiple different SILLs, resources, knowledge and skills available within ZeroW project, the spread across the 3 macro regions when it comes to involving and reaching stakeholders with the CBAs, and synergies with other ZeroW Tasks/activities or with other projects.

Based on the above inputs, WP6 leads brainstormed and proposed a first list of capacity building activities available in [Appendix I](#). Most activities were linked to one SILL, but some activities were relevant to multiple SILLs. The long list was reviewed with WP6 partners who contributed with suggestions, resulting in a final list of 37 relevant activities. These were proposed to the SILLs during online meetings between WP6 partners and the SILL coordinators. With their input, a joint decision was made for an activity per SILL, considering geographical spread across the three macro regions.

Table 4 Why, what, how per SILL to determine the preferred way of scaling

SILL	PROBLEM (from PTA)	WHY (“Systemic purpose” or mental model)	HOW	WHAT (“Product purpose”)
1. F2F FLW monitoring & assessment	lack of accurate and coherent data on FLW	To make the societal costs of food waste transparent for steering behaviour of stakeholders	By exposing what value goes to waste, e.g., in nutrition and CO2 and making sure the information reaches the right people	A data-driven platform that captures FLW data throughout the supply chain, and provide analytics to address requirements in the chain (e.g. SDGs)
2. Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh food products	FW due to (1) inaccurate date marking on and (2) unsustainable fish packaging	To influence consumption decisions on the spot by giving real-time insight into the actual quality of fresh produce	By developing informational (and biodegradable) packaging that can trigger certain decisions of the target group(s)	An ‘intelligent’ label that advises the consumer on the actual product quality based on measured product characteristics and retailer data
3. Wasteless greenhouse solutions for (pre)harvesting aligned with short-term downstream demand	Food loss resulting from substandard tomatoes or oversupply of tomatoes (the latter caused by farmers' risk management or supply and demand mismatch, or weather conditions).	To reduce insecurities for farmers so they can optimise their harvests and yield (instead of overproducing)	By reducing information asymmetries and giving actionable insight into potential yield, product quality and optimal harvest times	A data-driven monitoring and decision-making tool to better match supply and demand of fresh produce.

<p>4 Mobile food valorisation as a service</p>	<p>Diverse and volatile pre-consumer fruit & vegetable losses</p>	<p>To provide a flexible solution for valorising seasonal overproduction of fresh produce by turning them into high value finished products</p>	<p>By locally processing relatively small batches of fresh produce and edible fractions with limited costs</p>	<p>A mobile processing unit as a service & data platform, including developing recipes for the left-over produce</p>
<p>5 Ugly food early identification, shelf-life assessment & alternative valorisation</p>	<p>-Inaccurate and delayed shelf-life estimations-- Lack of automatic sorting according to quality and identification of ugly foods - Lack of fast and cost-effective technologies to discriminate organic from conventional products</p>	<p>To prove the value of 'ugly' food so less will be wasted</p>	<p>By providing producers with better quality information about their produce, so there is more time to define a market strategy</p>	<p>Data-driven solutions that can identify (the amounts of) ugly food earlier and assess quality and shelf-life</p>
<p>6 Food waste reduction through advanced data-driven production process control & optimisation</p>	<p>Current quality and process controls are: - not-continuous processes - based on judgement from operators - periodical samples that are time consuming and expensive This is causing FW</p>	<p>To allow timely corrective action in food production to reduce FLW during production.</p>	<p>Providing (real-time) objective steering information and pro-actively informing the workers</p>	<p>Developing, implementing and testing digital tools that give more information about food quality, and create a data-driven, fully controlled, proactive and optimised system</p>

<p>7 Food waste reduction through efficient food bank networks</p>	<p>While food is still being wasted in retail stores, food banks are faced with shortages</p>	<p>To ensure the provision of fresh food for people in need.</p>	<p>By making the food bank operations more in control of supply and demand</p>	<p>Innovative (digital) solutions such as prediction / forecasting; tools for donors; and tips (handbook) on food waste preventions</p>
<p>8 Retail food waste valorisation through algae production for high-value applications</p>	<p>How can we valorise food waste generated at retail level that is not suitable for donation/human consumption? Can we find a sustainable feedstock solution for cosmetics and biopolymers?</p>	<p>To add value to food streams that would normally go to waste and redirect them to algae production</p>	<p>Making the process of pre-treatment and reverse logistics of food feasible for in-store/warehouse settings</p>	<p>An end-to-end process from identification, on-site pre-treatment, packaging and transportation (reversed logistics)</p>
<p>9 Consumers choices & reverse (dietetics) and forward (FLW, sustainability etc) optimization</p>	<p>Consumers make suboptimal decisions related to meal planning and food purchasing, which lead to FW</p>	<p>To influence consumer food choices as they have a pivotal role in FLW reduction</p>	<p>Empowering consumers with advice to make food choices than can mutually benefit their own and society's wellbeing</p>	<p>Application of recent mathematical optimisation techniques and feed these into consumer interfaces</p>

Figure 4: Scaling out, scaling deep, scaling up. Adopted from Moore et al 2015.

2.2. Preparation of capacity building activities

2.2.1. SILL 1

SILL1 built a digital platform where FLW data can be stored, exchanged, and analysed. The goal is to create more insights into the various social, economic, and environmental impacts of FLW which can be shared with various stakeholders to increase motivations and abilities to tackle FLW issues (see [Table 4](#)).

Several meetings between WP6 and SILL1 partners were held to finetune the needs regarding capacity building for this SILL. The main challenges for the systemic solution being developed in this SILL were: (1) developing a Datahub Strategy (set out a vision and mission, how to finance and govern a Data Hub); (2) getting the datahub operational and interoperable through the implementation of a semantic treehouse, and (3) building a community of data providers and data users. The first challenge can be addressed by a joint development of a futureproof business model with stakeholder buy-in. The third challenge can be tackled by engaging stakeholders to join the data space by understanding who should be part of the ecosystem, what their needs are and ways to derive value out of the data space. These two activities took place in the context of WP7, through an actor mapping, value mapping, and Business Model Canvas exercises wherein the SILL's local stakeholders were involved. Hence, it was decided to focus on challenge 2: the need

to increase the SILL's knowledge on semantic interoperability. For this, TNO developed three half day workshops on how to implement a Semantic Treehouse (STH). Part one focused on the technical side and how to deploy STH, part two was more operational and the third part zoomed in on strategy and tactics. An executive summary is available in section 3.1 and [Annex V](#) features the extensive summary and detailed agenda of the workshops. Audio recordings and PowerPoints are available upon request.

2.2.2. SILL 2

SILL2 developed a smart label that visually reflects the actual state of a food product (fish) in a package in an easy-to-interpret way. The goal is to lower FLW by avoiding food waste due to conventional, inaccurate date marking. Additionally, an innovative, more sustainable packaging is being developed to postpone food spoilage through a smart physical design.

The main challenge identified for this SILL was to achieve consumer acceptance of and an enabling policy environment for the sustainable packaging materials and the smart label. Several workshop ideas were considered; demonstrating the benefits of the new packaging to manufacturers and food companies, including the actor's incentive model to demonstrate the impacts of implementing this new packaging. In the end we opted to work further on a consumer acceptance panel organised by SILL 2 partners. This panel gave important first insights into the willingness to buy and trust of consumers in high-tech packaging with a sustainable selling proposition. It was decided that these first insights needed to be placed in the existing literature on the topic of consumer attitudes towards more sustainable consumption and data labelling interpretation. A panel of external experts was composed by ILVO based on leading publication in this field. We brought together external specialists in marketing, psychology, food economics, and packaging innovation to assess the behavioural impact of the smart label and sustainable packaging. The aim was to generate actionable insights to improve design and communication strategies, and to support broader adoption of the solution in real-world retail settings.

2.2.3. SILL 3

SILL3 developed a technology that uses imaging techniques and AI to process this data and estimate the ripeness and quality of each tomato. This helps producers to harvest in a more targeted manner and adapt greenhouse parameters to match supply and demand better.

The main challenges identified for this SILLs' scaling potential are:

- 1) To sell the solution to the end users.

- 2) To set up a data space between the users of the technology (data owners) and the supplier of the technology/sensors. This could open up more data for the algorithm to be trained.
- 3) To create a marketplace between producers and processors where excess produce can be offered and found. Excess produce is the amount of food left after all contracts the farmer has closed, have been fulfilled.

For challenge 2, it was decided that activities to support this were already being organised within WP2 of the ZeroW project and it should not have been the focus of T6.2.

Addressing challenge three would be very difficult at this point according to the SILL3 coordinator. Building such a marketplace would be one thing, finding enough users to populate the marketplace would have proven to be tough at this point. The SILL coordinator preferred to work on the first challenge because it centres around the key issue, namely, to convince farmers to invest in this solution. Several possible CBAs to address this challenge were proposed by the WP6 lead to the SILL coordinator. After considering several options we opted to repeat the workshop form T6.1 but in the SILL region with large-scale high-tech farms to obtain more feedback on the practical implementation of the solution to be considered when designing scale up strategies. This workshop was organised by ART21 and Agrifood Lithuania with the support of ILVO. The workshop collected feedback from stakeholders and end users on the SILL 3 solution. We brought together producers, test centres, farmer organisations, researchers and policy makers to fully understand the opportunities and bottlenecks when bringing this technology to the market.

2.2.4. SILL 4

SILL 4 aimed to reduce fruit and vegetable loss caused by mismatches in supply and demand, unmet cosmetic or quality standards, and unsold retail stock. To address this, the living lab piloted a flexible processing unit that transforms small volumes of surplus produce into longer shelf-life products. This solution is particularly relevant for farmers with excess production and food redistribution organisations seeking a stable supply of nutritious food.

Initial testing revealed key lessons. Mobility of the unit added unnecessary complexity; instead, the focus should have been on flexibility. The current preservation method, Pulsed Electric Fields produced high-quality products but required chilled storage and offered only a 4–6 week shelf life, which posed logistical challenges. Switching to preservation techniques allowed ambient storage and up to one year of shelf life was recommended. Additionally, processing should have been handled by professionals rather than volunteers or farmers.

One promising feedstock for the unit is produce withdrawn from the market under the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). These are large volumes of uniform, edible fruits and vegetables. While EU and Flemish regulations encourage donation to social redistribution organisations, only 10% of withdrawn produce in Flanders is used for human consumption. Flemish law currently prohibits processing this produce into long shelf-life products, limiting its potential.

To explore solutions, SILL 4 conducted desk research and identified a successful case in Catalonia, Spain, where withdrawn produce was reprocessed for donation. A study visit to Barcelona was organised to understand the supply chain, regulatory context, and financial model. Flemish stakeholders were invited, and a follow-up policy workshop was held in Belgium to share insights and assess feasibility for local implementation.

The capacity building activity focused on increasing knowledge of food donation and market withdrawal regulations in Flanders and Europe, studying best practices for reprocessing withdrawn produce, and connecting relevant Flemish and Belgian stakeholders to explore the potential for replicating the Catalanian model.

2.2.5. SILL 5 and SILL 6

SILL5 developed data-driven solutions that can identify (the amounts of) ugly food earlier and assess their quality and shelf-life, to enable tomato producers to more timely determine suitable marketing strategies. SILL6 is developed technical solutions to provide real-time objective steering information about meat products to pro-actively inform the workers to avoid food waste due to food safety issues that are currently detected too late (see [Table 4](#)).

Both SILLs encountered similar challenges. The first challenge related to the acceptance of the solution from the producers or line personnel, and the second challenge related to the data sharing of the data with the users and the training of the algorithm. The second challenge, similar to SILL 3, was indicated to being tackled within T2.6 of the ZeroW project. Therefore, for these SILLs it was decided to build a CBA for addressing the first challenge (about technology acceptance) for complementarity reasons. Hence, the current plan is to organise 2 similar workshops (1 for Aldelis and 1 for GLC personnel) to increase their awareness about FLW problems and to make them see the benefits of the new tools, including how they can support or make their daily work easier.

The scope and aim of these workshops were co-created by TNO and ILVO and presented to and approved by the SILL5 and SILL6 coordinators during an online meeting on 8 October 2024. The scope, purpose and approach, and agenda for these workshops are included in [Appendix VI](#).

2.2.6. SILL 7

SILL7 aimed to support the alignment of surplus food and the demand for people in the need by providing (1) innovative (digital) solutions such as forecasting tools for donors and prediction tools for food banks and other charity organisations; and (2) guidelines (handbook) on food waste preventions.

There were multiple challenges identified. Firstly, to get the demand forecasting tool and donation tool aligned. Secondly, to make the donation transparent of capacity of retailers and provide incentives for retailers to engage in forecasting activities. If retailers would have shared data on expected food waste, this would have helped food banks plan in advance. The need to make the donation capacity of retailers transparent and provide incentives for retailers was identified as the bottleneck challenge for this SILL to be scaled. Thirdly, to achieve more centralised knowledge and data about the availabilities and skills of volunteers (schedules, skills, driving licenses, etc.) which could have helped plan the deployment of volunteers at crucial moments on sites that needed it at that moment.

Due to the bottleneck identity of challenge 2, it was unanimously decided to focus on this challenge. The initial idea was to map the different tax benefits for retailers to share their data on food surplus across EU and subsequently to organise a policy workshop about the most effective ones. However, over the course of the preliminary contact with industry it became apparent that tax mechanisms only contribute marginally to the decision-making process of retailers. Instead, dynamic pricing strategies were highlighted as the current most significant challenge (and therefore influence factor) when it comes to operational choices related to markdowns. To accommodate these practitioners' feedback, the CBA approach was pivoted to meet the industry challenge. Instead of a tax-focused workshop SILL7 partners contributed to two ECR Retail Loss & Food Waste seminars (April 9 and June 11 2025), where they were invited to speak by industry on the topic of dynamic pricing and markdown strategies. By pivoting based on the progressive insights the SILL7 CBA was able to meet (industry) practitioners needs, influencing real-life decision-making processes surrounding (the limitations of) markdown strategies.

2.2.7. SILL 8

SILL 8 aims to valorise food waste generated at retail level that is not suitable for donation or human consumption. To add value to these surplus food streams, that would normally go to waste, by using the surplus food to make a substrate to cultivate algae production (see [Table 4](#)).

Algae cultivation is emerging as a key approach for waste valorisation and circular economy objectives within the EU, particularly in the purification of waste by capturing excess nutrients while converting CO₂ to O₂. Microalgae biomass obtained from "waste treatment" can serve in a range of applications, from fertilisers and

animal feeds to high-value industrial uses such as cosmetics and biopolymers, as proposed by SILL 8 in the context of ZeroW. However, legal clarity is necessary to ensure these waste-derived products can enter the market securely and sustainably.

Several meetings between SILL 8 core partners (AllMicroalgae and mcSonae) were organised to discuss the needs of this SILL in terms of capacities needed for upscaling the solution. Finally, two core challenges were identified to be crucial for the further development of the SILL's solution. The first challenge related to getting the dehydrator certified. To address regulatory uncertainties, the ZeroW project's SILL 8 was aided by WP6 partners through online meeting discussions and email exchanges, desktop searches and contacts among colleagues. This research looked into the existing research on dehydrators and more specifically on their safety in terms of treating animal by-products. Looking at the EU and international level for these studies, but also which stakeholders are active in this. This was linked to the existing regulations and the expected changes. Subsequently, some of the actors were approached to obtain more support and if possible, information.

The second challenge concerns uncertainties of the use of waste to produce and commercialise microalgae biomass: there is a need to characterise the waste and repurpose it as a microalgae growth medium ingredient. Microalgae producers apply standard methods to produce the algae and require an analysis of the ingredients which are included into media formulations. In the context of ZeroW, work was performed to evaluate the nutrients and the storage (microbiology) of the waste, to address technical feasibility of the proposed solution. And, although proof-of-concept was achieved (see SILL 8 Periodic Report), the legal aspects and general product requirements are now under debate. For applications in all those different industries, different requirements might be in place, as well as different legal definitions of waste and/or by products. Understanding the legal framework for getting such applications marketed is a crucial part of this endeavour. To address these issues, SILL 8 partner Allmicroalgae participated in a workshop organised by the European Sustainable Phosphorus Platform (ESPP), under the theme "Legal Aspects of Algae", with a focus on legal status of biomass produced using waste, and its valorisation pathways. This event included experts from the European Commission, legal advisors, representatives from the European Algae Biomass Association (EABA), and various EU bioeconomy projects. The workshop emphasised the need for regulatory guidance to support investment and market expansion in algae-based solutions.

2.2.8. SILL 9

SILL9 addresses food waste at consumer level, by developing tools, methods, and interfaces to support households in planning their meals and groceries to stimulate more healthy and sustainable diets (see [Table 4](#)). Relevant data on sustainability of

food products and their health scores are the basis of this solution. Mapping this data with popular recipes that people use is crucial to really achieve an impact. The capacity building activity for this SILL initially focussed on how data sharing between consumers and supermarkets could be achieved. However, renewed insights during the last year revealed a potential larger gap when it came to making this innovation a reality: critical stakeholders might be missing from the equation to produce a systemic result. Specifically, current partners both subject to institutional restriction when it comes to financial investments and long-term maintenance of the app. By open sourcing the prototype code the partners hope to attract industrial or private institutes that will take up a role in the realisation of the innovation. It was therefore decided to use this opportunity as an active call to action, for external partners to build capacity based on their work and to take their innovation to the next stage.

3. Report on execution of capacity building activities

3.1 SILL 1

Twenty participants joined the workshops spread over three days. Most participants joined all three sessions and some only one or two. Most participants were from ITC or Transilvania Cluster, the two leaders of SILL 1. Other participants were from related universities and a farmer advisory board. On top of the twenty participants, we also had people from ILVO and TNO joining the call to facilitate, provide content or ensure linkages with other project tasks and the systemic approach within the ZeroW project.

The workshop was split up into three parts with each their own focus and a slightly different target group. The first workshop was a technical demonstration of how to deploy the software Semantic Treehouse (STH). In the second workshop we zoomed out and demonstrated how STH can be used as a platform to create and maintain shared data models together, resulting in interoperability. The last workshop we zoomed out even further and discussed strategies and tactics to establish an inter-organisational collaboration framework that is required before a tool like STH can be used purposefully. Below is a summary of the workshops, the full report and slides are available in [Annex V](#).

Semantic interoperability refers to the ability of different systems and organisations to exchange data in a way that preserves its meaning. It ensured that shared data is interpreted consistently across platforms, sectors, and stakeholders. This is achieved through common data models and semantic agreements that define how information is structured, labelled, and understood. STH facilitates this process by offering a collaborative platform where communities can build, maintain, and evolve shared semantic standards. It replaces static documents with dynamic, interactive repositories that track changes, discussions, and validations. This approach is

particularly valuable in complex ecosystems where multiple actors need to coordinate based on shared understanding, such as agriculture, logistics, and public services.

In the context of the ZeroW project, semantic interoperability is a key enabler for reducing food waste. Miscommunication and inconsistent data interpretation across the supply chain often led to inefficiencies, overproduction, and spoilage. By aligning definitions of quality, ripeness, shelf life, and waste categories, STH helps stakeholders make better-informed decisions. The ZeroW Semantic Treehouse environment, already deployed by TNO, allows users to access and build upon the ZeroW ontology. This supports the creation of new data models tailored to food waste reduction, enabling services such as crop monitoring, predictive analytics, and waste tracking. The platform empowers farmers, processors, and retailers to collaborate more effectively, ultimately contributing to a more resilient and efficient food system.

Despite its potential, several barriers to implementing STH were identified during the workshops:

- **Technical complexity:** Deploying STH using Kubernetes requires advanced skills and infrastructure, which may be inaccessible to smaller organisations.
- **Community engagement:** The platform's value depends on active participation. Without a committed user base, standards cannot evolve or be maintained.
- **Governance and maintenance:** Sustaining a common data model requires long-term coordination, funding, and clear ownership structures.
- **Trust and collaboration:** Low levels of trust or unfamiliarity between stakeholders can hinder data sharing, especially in fragmented sectors.
- **Business model uncertainty:** Transitioning from a project phase to a sustainable initiative requires a viable funding model and strategic planning.

The workshops explored various business models from other sectors to inform future sustainability:

- **SETU (Flexible Staffing):** Standards are free to use. Funding comes from major companies who benefit most, supplemented by small fees from software vendors.
- **Ketenstandaard (Construction):** A pay-per-use model based on company revenue. While it introduces a barrier, it ensures financial sustainability and direct user engagement.
- **OpenTrip (Transport & Logistics):** Maintained by an open-source community with minimal central funding. No fees are charged for use or participation.

These models showed that sustainability depends on context. A key decision is whether to establish a new organisation or integrate with an existing standardisation body. The B.O.M.O.S. model offers guidance on governance and

strategic choices for open standards. STH supports a decentralised approach, allowing local representatives to coordinate participation and manage subscriptions.

As the ZeroW project concludes, stakeholders must consider how to sustain the Semantic Treehouse platform and its community. Key steps include:

- Defining a clear value proposition for using STH in food systems.
- Engaging early adopters with practical tools and fast benefits.
- Establishing governance and funding mechanisms, possibly through existing sector bodies.
- Providing validation and certification services to support implementation and build trust.
- Fostering a collaborative culture, where data sharing is seen as mutually beneficial.

In conclusion, STH is not just a technical tool, it is a strategic enabler for systemic change. It's success depends on community engagement, governance, and sustainable business models. When applied to food systems, it offers a powerful pathway to reduce inefficiencies and food loss across the value chain.

3.2 SILL 2

The expert panel took place online on 14/05/2025, 3 experts participated along with SILL2 and WP6 partners. The detailed list of participants is available in [annex VII](#)

The workshop started with a brief introduction of the ZeroW project and SILL 2 in particular. The setup and key findings of the consumer panel study (23 participants) were explained to ensure that everyone was on the same page. A full report of this study was shared beforehand.

Consumer Panel summary

The consumer panel participants self-reported wasting less than 5% of their food on a weekly basis. Participants in the consumer panel cited several common reasons for discarding food, including undesirable appearance, unpleasant smell, expiry dates, and uncertainty regarding safety. These factors highlight the challenges consumers face in assessing food freshness and safety, often relying heavily on expiry labels that may not accurately reflect the product's condition. The introduction of a smart label was met with strong interest from the consumer panel. Designed to provide a more reliable indication of freshness, the label was seen as particularly useful in reducing uncertainty and minimizing dependence on traditional expiry dates. Notably, 90% of participants expressed trust in the smart label, indicating a clear preference for this innovation over conventional labelling methods. During the panel, consumers were asked if they would buy packaging with

extra benefits (such as extended shelf life or smart labels), even if it was less visually attractive. 90% said yes, and 10% said maybe. When asked if they would be willing to purchase a product with this type of packaging in the future, 100% of participants responded positively.

Expert discussion

Despite promising insights, the experts point out that the consumer panel faced several limitations. The sample size was relatively small, with only 23 participants, which restricts the statistical generalisability of the findings. Recruitment was conducted in-store, introducing a self-selection bias that may have skewed the participant pool toward more engaged or environmentally conscious consumers.

The self-reported food waste level of 5% is very low compared to the average household food waste levels. Experts see several explanations for this. The above-mentioned selection bias could have been at play as well as a social desirability bias due to the face-to-face format of the panel. Since the study did not provide a clear definition of “food waste,” it is possible that misunderstandings about what constitutes food waste affected the accuracy of self-reported data. For example, Australian consumers discard food in organic compost bins, thinking that it is not food waste because it is going to be composted anyway.

It's important to note that food waste patterns vary significantly by product category and geographic region. High-value items such as fish and meat tend to be wasted less frequently than staple foods, which may influence the perceived effectiveness of smart packaging across different food types.

The experts pointed out that there is a notable gap between participants stated intentions and their actual behaviour. While many participants in the consumer panel expressed a willingness to pay for smart packaging solutions, real-world purchasing decisions may not align with these claims. This discrepancy demonstrated the complexity of consumer motivations and the influence of factors such as price, convenience, and habit. While sustainability is an important factor in purchase decisions, it will not justify larger price increases. The focus should be on communicating other messages directly benefiting consumers such as convenience and increased food safety giving consumers peace of mind.

Sensory cues, such as appearance and smell along with expiry dates and safety concerns, were the primary drivers of food disposal. The smart label aims to address these issues by offering a more accurate and trustworthy freshness indicator, potentially reducing unnecessary waste and improving consumer confidence.

The design of the SILL 2 packaging uses smileys; they are judged to be great visual cues that are easy to understand. The label also uses a colour scale, and this is judged to be confusing since it gives a gradual scale while consumers need to know

if food is safe to eat or not. Experts suggested to include text labels to direct consumers towards the label and provide short instructions on how to interpret the colour label. Positioning it near the date marks will create an association between the two and facilitate easier decision-making by having two bits of information in close proximity. Other icons could be explored, and the icons could be printed in the reference colour to minimise visual clutter.

The workshop concluded with several key recommendations to enhance the impact of smart packaging and reduce food waste:

- In-depth interviews to better understand the drivers of food waste behaviour.
- Consumer Education: There is a pressing need to educate consumers about food waste, how to assess freshness, and the role packaging can play in extending shelf life.
- Clear Definitions and Methodologies: Establishing standardized definitions and robust methods for measuring food waste is essential for future research and policy development.
- Product-Specific Strategies: Tailored approaches, such as freezing for certain items, can help maximize the effectiveness of smart packaging.
- Innovative packaging and smart labels have potential to reduce food waste, especially for products where uncertainty about freshness is a major driver of disposal.
- Expanded Testing: Larger and more representative samples are needed to validate the findings and ensure broader applicability.

Environmental considerations were also discussed. The ZeroW Tray, aligns with sustainability goals and offers a promising alternative to traditional packaging. However, concerns remain about the reliability of smart labels and the potential erosion of consumer trust if the technology fails to deliver consistent results. The recoding of this workshop is available upon request.

3.3 SILL 3

The CBA Workshop for SILL 3 took place on January 28th, 2025, in Anykščiai, Lithuania. The session was organised by Agrifood DIH Lithuania, following a workshop template developed by ILVO. A total of 19 participants attended, representing a diverse mix of stakeholders including greenhouse producers, technology providers, government officials, and experts from agricultural associations.

The workshop focused on the challenge of matching supply and demand in greenhouse tomato production, a topic that resonated strongly with all participants. The group unanimously recognized the difficulty of aligning production with market needs, particularly in northern climates like Lithuania where environmental

unpredictability and higher energy demands complicate planning. Participants emphasized that without precise harvest timing, return on investment is significantly reduced. They also noted that natural factors often disrupt predictable production cycles, requiring growers to constantly adjust ripening schedules.

The discussion revealed that while the technology presented during the workshop - an AI-based solution for harvest forecasting and disease detection - is functional and promising, it still requires initial calibration to the specific conditions of each greenhouse and tomato variety. This need for customisation was identified as a potential barrier to scaling, especially for smaller farms with limited technical support. Participants stressed that successful implementation would require close collaboration between growers and technicians to fine-tune the system.

Another systemic success factor identified was the existing digital infrastructure. Most participants reported having access to the necessary systems and equipment, which lowers the barrier to adoption. Additionally, the solution was perceived as user-friendly, and participants felt confident in their ability to use it. However, around 50% of the group indicated that training would be necessary, particularly for operational staff. Tailored training programs in local languages, with practical demonstrations, were suggested to accelerate adoption and build confidence.

Despite the overall enthusiasm, several obstacles to scaling were discussed. One major concern was resistance to change among employees. Participants noted that many staff members are comfortable with current workflows and may be reluctant to adopt new technologies. This cultural barrier could hinder implementation unless addressed through targeted change management strategies. Furthermore, while the solution was seen as a step toward future-proofing production, participants pointed out that it currently lacks integration with weather data and pest detection, features they consider essential for accurate forecasting.

The conversation also touched on economic feasibility. Most participants found the solution affordable, but its cost-effectiveness depends on farm size, available subsidies, and long-term return on investment. Smaller producers may require financial support or incentives to adopt the technology.

In terms of food waste reduction, the group was generally optimistic. The solution's ability to forecast harvests and detect diseases early was seen as a key enabler for minimizing waste and improving market planning. Accurate harvest forecasting would allow for better alignment with demand, reducing overproduction and spoilage. Participants also highlighted the importance of internal communication and workflow adjustments to ensure smooth integration of the new system. While these changes were considered feasible, they require time, coordination, and support from management.

Finally, the workshop underscored the importance of a system-wide approach. Participants agreed that technology alone is not enough to address the challenges

of supply-demand alignment and food waste. A broader strategy involving improved crop management, better communication, and incentives for quality production is essential. The workshop served as a valuable opportunity to inform stakeholders about the efforts being made within the ZeroW project and to gather insights that will help guide future development and implementation.

3.4 SILL 4

3.4.1. Study trip Barcelona

This study trip took place on 24 & 25th of October 2024. We were joined by representatives from social redistribution organisations (Foodbanks and Foodsavers), ZeroW project partners, a social entrepreneur and the Catalan department of agriculture. The detailed list of participants can be found in [appendix II](#) and a report on the different site visits in [appendix III](#). Below we zoom in on the policy workshop as this was the central focus of this capacity building activity.

3.4.2. Policy workshop Brussels, Belgium

Location and participants

This workshop took place on November 20th, 2024, in Brussels. All relevant government departments were represented. At the Flemish level, we had the Departments of Health and Wellbeing, Agriculture and Fisheries, and the Public Waste Agency represented. The local level was represented by the Organisation of Cities and Communities. The federal level was represented by the Department for Social Integration. On the side of the donating companies, three out of four producer organisations participated: BelOrta, REO, and Hoogstraten – supported by their umbrella organisation. On the side of the social organisations, both FoodSavers and FoodBanks participated. Finally, we invited a social entrepreneur, and ILVO represented the research side. The detailed list of participants can be found in [appendix IV](#).

Presentation of the regulation on market withdrawals by the Flemish Agency of Agriculture and Fisheries

The Flemish Agency of Agriculture and Fisheries presented the regulatory framework of taking produce out of the market and explains the challenges in controlling these processes. This is part of European Regulations 2022/2015 & 2021/126.

How does the financing work?

A country needs to include the mechanism of market withdrawals in its' strategic plan that needs to be submitted under the common agricultural policy (CAP). A specific producer organisation (PO) needs to include this mechanism in their own operational plan. Flemish PO's sell their produce via the clock; this system is unique

to Flanders and The Netherlands. This implies that the control and redistribution of the produce needs to happen very quickly since the quantity of unsold produce is determined around lunchtime. PO's that work with contracts know days in advance how much surplus they will have.

When produce are withdrawn, the farmer receives a compensation, this is financed via European CAP budget and co-financed by the PO's. The compensation is determined by Europe for some product in R. 2022/126. For some products: tomatoes, cauliflower, apple, pear, (water)melon, egg plant the compensation is determined by the members states, in Flanders this is described in R. 2022/126 – article 26.2. The compensation is partly linked to the product and partly to cover sorting and packaging. The total compensation can never be higher than 80% of the average market prices over the last three years as determined in 2022/126 – article 26.1.

The compensation is only allowed when the produce is sent to one of the following destinations:

- Donation (=human consumption) this results in a compensation that is +/- 30% higher than for the other destinations. On top of that the percentage of co-financing for the PO's is lower.
- Animal Feed
- Biogas production (note that this is not an allowed destination in Spain).

Social redistribution organisation receives a compensation for transport.

How are the controls organised?

Currently there are 4 PO's that use the mechanism of market withdrawals in Flanders, in Wallonia this is not implemented. In 2023 13.750 tonnes of fruit and vegetables were taken out of the market in Flanders and 12% (1650 tonnes) was donated to a social redistribution organization.

Social organisations that want to pick up the produce that is taken out of the market need a special permit (Access pas type 1). To obtain this they need to be a non-profit organisation and have a structural collaboration with a social welfare institution, a foodbank or another social service. There are other types of permits available linked to the allowed destinations for this withdrawn produce:

- Access pas type 1: social welfare organisations, food related (77 in Flanders)
- Access pas Type 2: hospitals and youth organisations (35 in Flanders)
- Access pas Type 4A: farmers and animal parks (animal food) à this is the main destination of the PO surplus produce (28 in Flanders)
- Access pas Type 4B: biogas à this happens only in exceptional circumstances (5 in Flanders)

The agency controls not only the Flemish but also 22 social organisations and animal parks in Wallonia and Brussels.

The auctions get a lot of requests from citizens who want to redistribute surplus food on their own, they all need to be disappointed because this is not allowed. The auctions refer them to the Foodbanks or Foodsavers, these are large platforms who redistribute the food to 673 local food redistribution organisations. However, some of these local food redistribution organisations historically obtained an access pas type 1 and thus pick up food themselves at the PO's. This results in a lot of smaller organisations regularly picking up small quantities of food at the PO's and creating complexity for both the PO's and the controlling authority. The controlling authority works with a team of 5 FTE to control the large platforms and the 673 local social redistribution organisations in Belgium (even though this is a department of the Flemish government) and the 4 PO's who make use of this system.

The agency needs to check if the produce withdrawn is fresh as well as the produce that is redistributed. The quality and food safety needs to be guaranteed. The Agency checks if the PO's respect the quality and quantity. The Agency also checks if the social organisations are respecting the administrative requirements, distributing the good for free and to the right people. The other destinations are off course also controlled.

The local food redistribution organisations are not allowed to 'sell' these products. This is sometimes challenging for social grocery shops where people pay a small fee but can choose themselves what they want to take home (versus a prepacked box of goods). This increases their dignity but is not allowed for produce taken out of the market and FEAD products. The organisations are allowed to ask a small fee for handling and logistics, but this needs to be an overall cost and not linked to the FEAD products or the products taken out of the market.

How can we get more fresh fruit and vegetables to people in need?

Reducing the number of organisations with 'access pas type 1' by clustering them would be needed according to the agency of agriculture and fisheries. This is not the expertise nor responsibility of the agency and requires close collaboration with other departments. This is the first time we have all the relevant authorities together in a meeting and a good starting point. However, due to GDPR it is not possible to share the names of these different organisations with VVSG for example.

We also need a better regional spread of the products across the country. Currently products coming from a PO in a certain region, remain in that region.

Processing these products into long shelf-life products is currently not allowed and would bring some challenges. Neither is there a budget at the Agency of Agriculture and fisheries to pay for the processing. However, there is an option to finance this via EIP projects.

PO's indicate that sometimes produce is disqualified for donation because it does not meet the trade norm due to a 'wrong' product description. For example, green peppers that are turning red or vine tomatoes that are not all on a vine. This happens sometimes but less and less according to the agency; they stress the importance of sticking to trade norms but also state that close interaction between the PO's and the Agency can help to avoid those situations.

Structure of food redistribution platforms in Belgium

Etienne Rubens from the Foodbanks and Arnout Vercruyssen from Food Act 13 (Foodsavers) present how both organisations operate and collaborate with each other. Foodbanks were founded in 1986 with the aim of fighting food insecurity and food waste. They redistribute food that is donated by large retailers, industry and the PO's. Foodbanks also distribute the food that was bought with the ESF+ budget, and they buy some food themselves. In total they (re)distributed 23.571 tonnes of food in 2023. Only 2% of this comes from the donations of the PO's. (note that the total quantity of withdrawn produce, 13.750 tonnes could cover more than half of the food distributed by the foodbanks). They redistribute to 673 local social redistribution organisations who reach 213.873 people in need every month. The foodbanks consist of a Belgian federation and 9 depots in the different provinces. Each depot has their own warehouse, fridges and logistical operations.

Foodsavers was launched by local governments 10 years ago after a call from POD MI with Food Act 13 and supported by the department of Health and Wellbeing. Their goal is not only to reduce food waste and food insecurity but also to employ people who have a distance to the labour market. It consists of 13 regional redistribution platforms that pick up food surplus at PO's and local retailers. Foodsavers is a Flemish organisation covering most, but not all, provinces. They promise the local retailers to pick up all the leftovers on a daily basis – this is important and was not done previously. Foodsavers then distributes the food to local social redistribution organisations, the same organisations that pick up produce at the regional food bank depots. Foodsavers wants to work as much as possible from the demand side, they prepare a different mix of goods for the different organisations depending on what their need is.

The collaboration between Foodbanks and Foodsavers is very strong in some regions (West-Vlaanderen and Limburg) and needs to be further developed in other regions. Since both foodbanks and Foodsavers pick up food at the PO's they have organised themselves so as to bundle this. Foodbanks West-Vlaanderen pick up products at REO auctions and redistribution is done via Foodsavers. There are four/five Foodbanks and 4 Foodsavers that pick up food at the PO's. They do this every week. Up until today they only receive vegetables and sometimes strawberries. The total quantities of food received from the PO's is declining, this is partly due to the Foodsavers but it seems that there is an overall decline. The total

amount collected by Foodsavors and Foodbank in 2023 is 812 tonnes (of the total of 1650 tonnes that is donated by the PO's).

The collaboration between the social redistribution organisations and the PO's works very well. Every week they are in contact via email or phone to align the quantities and pick up. All the large platforms are able to collect large quantities in crates and manage the return flow and administration. Currently Foodsavors nor Foodbanks are able to do processing into long shelf-life products but Foodsavors want to evolve in this direction. They do note that social organisations often make fresh soup as well and that this has an important connecting function that should not be replaced by this long shelf-life soup project.

In the Flavour project they calculated the social value of the Foodbanks and Foodsavors, every €1 invested in these organizations results in €8 to €9 social return on investment. The Foodbanks have generated €400 million social return on investment.

Foodsavors and Foodbanks would like to focus on the following issues:

There is much more food available, how can we increase the percentage of withdrawn fruit and vegetables that is donated to foodbanks and foodsavors?

What can we do to receive more fruit, specifically hard fruit? Even in pallets if this is the only way.

Can we consider processing of peak volumes into long shelf life products?

Foodsavors wants to transition into circular food hubs, the Flemish government is supporting this and also wants them to look into collecting post-harvest surplus produce from farmers.

Producer organisations in Flanders

Three out of four producer organisations that use the mechanism of taking produce out of the market are present in the meeting. All producer organisations present in Belgium were contacted prior to the meeting to see if they were interested in this topic. REO, Belorta and Hoogstraten each present the type of produce they have in surplus and the barriers they face when donating to the social redistribution platforms. Green Farm is the fourth PO and was not able to join this meeting but will be kept informed of the projects' evolution.

REO auctions

REO tries to respect the food waste pyramid as much as possible and never sends the food they take out of the market to biogas producers, they aim for human consumption or animal food. They do not want external people in their warehouse so the social organisations need to come with a truck to load the goods. The goods are stored in blue crates and the organisations pay a warranty to make sure the empty crates find their way back to REO. Smaller quantities are sometimes left

outside for pickup. But in general they always refer smaller organisations to the foodbanks or to Foodsavers. A challenge they face is that all the organisations want to come pickup goods on Monday and Tuesday but a lot less on Wednesday and nobody comes on Thursday and Friday (except for Foodsavers Gent). It is not possible to store the goods for more than a day since the quality needs to be perfect at the moment of donation and controlling. The unpredictable and highly variable offer of surplus products is a major challenge.

Reo auctions shares the quantities of withdrawn fruit and vegetables for 2023 and 2024, we see that a lot of lettuce, tomatoes, cucumber and zucchini are taken out of the market. Total market withdrawals were 50% lower in 2024 compared to 2023 due to the high prices. The proportion that was donated to social redistribution organisations increased from 15% in 2023 to 21% in 2024. In absolute terms this is however still a decrease of the total volume that is donated.

Auction Hoogstraten

In Hoogstraten they aim to reduce the number of withdrawals as much as possible. A new contract with a processing company that buys the surplus produce up to a certain annual amount has helped to reduce the number of withdrawals. Normally they start withdrawals as of May but now this starts only in June. The withdrawn produce is donated as much as possible, but in some cases they still need to send it to animal feed or exceptionally to biogas production. To maximise donations Hoogstraten does the effort of preparing mixed pallets for the smaller social redistribution organisations, this generates a lot of work for the PO but they try to do this. Pickup and control of the goods is done on Tuesday and Thursday, the collaboration is very good.

They mainly have to withdraw tomatoes, peppers, cucumbers and strawberries. Products that contain too much water and are not very interesting for biogas production. The peak is very high, in 2023 they had to dispose of 1000 pallets in one month!

The total quantity of withdrawn fruit and vegetables in 2024 was 588 tonnes which is a lot lower than in 2023 when 2838 tonnes were withdrawn from the market. Similar to REO the proportion that was donated to social redistribution organisations increased from 17% in 2023 to 58% in 2024. In absolute terms this is however still a decrease of the total volume that is donated.

Belorta auctions

Belorta also avoids sending food to biogas production, but it does happen in about 5% of the cases. Similar to REO auctions the total market withdrawals in 2024 were much lower (2500 tonnes) versus 2023 (10.000 tonnes). The proportion that was donated increased a lot from 10% in 2023 to 20% in 2024.

Belorta Sint Katelijne Waver (vegetables) stores the market withdrawals in a separate warehouse where the controlling can take place and the social redistribution organisations can come and transfer the products into their own crates on Monday, Wednesday and Friday. A forklift driver of Belorta supports these operations. On Monday the produce are collected by large social redistribution hubs (Foodbanks and Foodsavers) on Wednesday and Friday it is collected by 30 to 40 smaller organisations.

Belorta Borgloon (hard fruit) does not donate to social redistribution organisations because these goods are stored in palloxes and would need to be restacked in crates to comply with the current legislation. Even though these are longer shelf life products they also become available for donation in large quantities at the same time. This is due to speculation and large ULO storage rooms that need to be emptied once opened. Sometimes palloxes are mixed resulting in overall lower quality produce that is no longer fit for donation. Due to the retirement of responsible for this segment it might be easier to explore new ways of handling these products.

Belorta does not own any processing installations, this does not appear to be profitable for them.

Can farmers sell surplus products via other channels than their PO?

This depends from PO to PO. Often, they can be a member of more than one PO if these are in a different segment, for example it is allowed to be a member of fresh and frozen PO. It is also allowed to sell a part (25%) of their harvest in a short chain system but not to a processor, this is European legislation.

Lessons learned in Barcelona

ILVO briefly summarises the main lessons learned from the study trip to Barcelona, see full report in [annex III](#).

- Different market organisations:
- selling by the clock complicates redistribution and controlling of withdrawals (this is done only in Belgium, The Netherlands and a little bit in France)
- more diverse offer of fruit and vegetables throughout the year
- peaks of surplus for some products (oranges, nectarines) is unavoidable and solved via processing into long shelf life products
- Integrated food redistribution network in Barcelona makes collaboration with PO's and government easier.
- Political responsibility of food waste and food redistribution is clustered in one department – compared to very complex structure in Belgium/Flanders
- Overall the quantity of food withdrawn from the market is much lower in Barcelona, but almost all of it is reused for human consumption.

- Additional government support for Foodbanks to allow processing into long shelf life products.
- Several commercial and non-commercial organizations that work with surplus food and repurpose it for human consumption in Barcelona, this seems much more challenging in Belgium.

Lessons learned from previous soup projects

Previous projects that used surplus vegetables to produce soup resulted in some lessons learned:

- The production cost of these soups is much higher than for soup produced in regular large scale supply chains: between €3,6 and €6 per litre.
- Another complexity faced was the conservation technique. Existing social production sites used to be focused on producing fresh soup for schools and did not sterilise the soup but used pasteurisation. This resulted in a product with a relatively short shelf life (6 weeks) and a cold supply chain requirement. Cold supply chains are more expensive and very challenging for social redistribution organisations.
- To make year round production possible the project stored summer surplus in the freezer.
- The target group was not always interested in the end product, important to involve them in new attempts to launch such a project.
- There are two subgroups in the target group
- People who want to prepare their own hot meals
- People who want to ready-made meals
- The call for proposals required the production to be done by a social employment organisation, work with agricultural surplus and produce a nutritional soup. There was only one consortium that was able to fulfil these requirements. This market has developed somewhat in the meantime but it is still a niche market.
- For future projects it is suggested to integrate it in other local ESF initiatives so that the training and employment aspect can be covered by them and the 'FEAD' budget only needs to cover the food cost.

Competent authorities and budget

A preparatory meeting with the POD MI clarified the working of ESF+ in Belgium. Members states can decide to apply for this budget but need to co-finance. The current budget is granted until 2027 and there are rumours that Europe will drastically cut this budget while the demand for food aid is increasing. Belgium has co-funded more than was required, especially during the Covid crisis. The ESF+ money is used to purchase 25 different products that are complementary to the donated goods. The data on which products are donated is based on information obtained from the Foodbanks and thus omits what Foodsavors receive from local

retailers or other donations that are not reported. These goods are purchased via public procurement and divided among the Foodbanks based on the amount of social welfare beneficiaries in each province.

Food aid is considered as emergency aid, and this is the responsibility of the federal government and municipalities. ESF+ budget for food purchases and VAT on donations are all part of the federal government. However, the fight against poverty is the responsibility of the Flemish department of welfare. Foodsavers were launched with money from this department in collaboration with municipalities. Fighting poverty links very closely with (social) employment and this is the responsibility of the Flemish department of work and social economy. While the withdrawals of fruit and vegetables from the market is the responsibility of the Flemish Agency of Agriculture and Fisheries. It is clear that the responsibilities are very divided.

Food has the potential to reconnect people. Handing out food packs is necessary but whenever possible it is important to use food to get poor people to come out of their homes and meet other people. This is an important aspect of getting out of poverty. The number of people in poverty (income is only 60% of less of the median) is diminishing slightly but the number of people requesting food aid is increasing.

Political interest in organising emergency aid in a structural manner, i.e. investing in it, is very low. Nobody is very interested in assuming this responsibility and thus the budgets and responsibilities remain scattered among different departments and different regulatory levels. The adagium is that we need to give people in poverty a job so that they can buy their own food. Organising food redistribution is thus only an emergency measure.

Social entrepreneurs working with food surplus

Harvie is presented by Eric Demaeght, a social entrepreneur active in Brussels. He was involved in the Envie project launched by Colruyt, Reo auctions and McCain. The goal of that project was to produce soup from agricultural surplus and sell these in the Colruyt. However, selling a product made from surplus (and thus higher production costs) requires premium branding and this was not compatible with the 'Boni' brand (Colruyts' private label).

Eric decided to continue working with the chef from Envie and the production installation to produce high quality products (65 – 85% of vegetables in the soup) made from agricultural surplus. The soup is sterilised to have a long shelf life end product. He collaborates with a social employment firm as much as possible. The products are sold via high end shops but he has spare capacity and would love to produce soup for schools or other public institutions but this appears to be very complicated to achieve.

Discussion

We focused the discussion on two aspects:

- How can we increase direct donations?
- How can we cope with the high peaks of surplus products? Do we need to explore the possibility of processing into long shelf life products?

To increase direct donations there are a couple of **quick wins**:

- Add apples and other hard fruit to the donations
- Implement the system of warranty on the crates to avoid restacking
- Investigate the opportunity to pick up goods all days of the week

To increase direct donations on a larger scale more **structural changes** are needed. Apart from storage space and logistical capacity there is a need for more collaboration and coordination. Processes need to be mapped and optimised. This is happening already in a bottom up way but there seems to be lack of coordination. Social organisations can possibly learn from each other, for example how is Foodsavers Ghent organising their pick up on Fridays? VVSG indicates that they want to set out a vision for collaboration of social organisations and municipalities. Many smaller social organisations seem reluctant to collaborate with larger organisations. The different roles and responsibilities are often unclear. While we need to install trust and create a shared vision. VVSG points out that they will not be able to fulfil this coordination but can be part of the solution by working on the shared vision.

The group notes that the peaks of surplus are so high that it is impossible to distribute them all and even small scale processing would be challenging. For example Harvie can produce 1200 liter/day but would not be able to process 1000 pallets of tomatoes in one month. Investing in local small scale processing is not cheap, for example the estimated cost for the FoodAct 13 project to have a space for processing already costs €350.000.

Another important factor is the transparency of data, a digital platform that facilitates donations. Such a platform exists (<https://www.schenkingsbeurs.be/>) but is accessible for all social organisations and not only for platforms. This would make it easier to ensure the geographical division of the produce and simplify processes for the PO's (input on one system).

It is important to always ensure that we do not move the waste further down the chain. This needs to be monitored and evaluated.

Conclusion

There seems to be a potential to use surplus agricultural production to feed people in need. The quantity of withdrawn produce is already half of what the Foodbanks distribute. However, this requires infrastructure and logistics. From the point of view of the POD MI it appears to be cheaper to purchase food then to redistribute and

process the surplus food. Would this however still be the case when we take into account the CO2 impact and the monetary cost of wasting perfectly edible food for animal feed and biogas? In addition the redistribution and processing of surplus food could be linked to social employment like Espigoladores demonstrate in Barcelona and Harvie in Belgium.

At present we see that the collection of withdrawn fruit and vegetables is scattered. Only half (812 tonnes) of the total amount of withdrawn fruit and vegetables that is donated (1650 tonnes), goes directly to the Foodbanks or the Foodsavors. This indicates that a lot of small organisations collect a lot of produce. Social organisations do not have the capacity to restructure this on their own, structural support is needed to optimise this way of working. This needs to be done in a careful manner since the combination of small organisations represent a large share of the redistributed food and without them a lot more food would go to waste while people in need are in need of food.

The participants to the meeting all agree that this is the right combination of people to be able to tackle these issues. Follow up meetings will be planned in the framework of ZeroW SILL 4.

3.5 SILL 5

The workshop took place on January 28th at the offices of Grupo La Caña (GLC) and was organised by the GLC representative in the ZeroW project based on a template developed by WP 6 partners ILVO and TNO. As requested, a very diverse group of GLC personnel and SILL partners attended the workshop, 22 participants in total including:

- Warehouse personnel
- Warehouse quality internal auditor, assigns quality to the batches of fruits coming from the farmers
- Development director, director of the development department, with a lot of different tasks in la caña (innovation, IOT, engineering...)
- Warehouse manager, manages clients order, production, worker in the warehouse
- Quality certifications, focused on quality control, manages claims and certification for clients
- Line manager, manage a line of production, calibration or packaging

The workshop started with a general food waste quiz to share some basic insights on food loss and waste. The group was well aware of the large amounts of food being wasted and the fact that this mainly happens at household level. This triggered a discussion on the causes of this household food waste and how to avoid it. Better planning, more frequent shopping and remembering what is in your fridge is judged to be important. Interestingly they also mention that the shelf life of fruit and

vegetables differs between cheaper versus more expensive supermarkets. Participants indicate that this challenging mainly due to time constraints. The group feels that there is room for more awareness raising campaigns on this topic.

After this personal reflection on food waste, we moved on to discussing food waste in the professional context of GLC. Overall, participants believe that the company is making efforts but faces significant pressure from clients (supermarkets, etc.) and challenges in waste management. However, one participant disagrees, stating that, from her perspective, the company's main priority is fulfilling orders, and she does not see food loss or waste management as a key concern.

In more detail, the participants working in certification and quality, believe that GLC is paying attention to waste management. They are all aware of the development of new products by GLC, which involve transformation processes (such as gazpacho, salmorejo, etc.) to repurpose products that cannot be sold due to aesthetic reasons. More operational participants such as plant managers expressed that the company's main focus is preparing products on time to meet client demands, regardless of the waste generated.

Informing this diverse group of employees on the efforts GLC is taking to reduce food waste in projects like ZeroW was therefore a valuable exercise, as most were previously unaware of them.

After presenting the technical solution of the multisensor platform and NG sensor the participants agreed that this could be an opportunity to reduce FLW. This platform would allow GLC to identify ripe fruit early on and find alternative commercialisation channels (salmorejo, gazpacho, ...). Some plant workers were hesitant, mainly due to concerns about the equipment's operational efficiency rather than the solution itself. Interestingly they also highlighted other key factors that need to be addressed to minimize losses, such as maintaining machinery that damages fruit, controlling environmental conditions (temperature, humidity, and gases), and ensuring proper pre-harvest management. To encourage better practices, they suggested rewarding farmers who take better care of their crops and generate fewer losses.

After the plenary presentation the group was split in 3 smaller groups with 3 to 5 participants. The subgroups were split in such a way to have a good mix of warehouse personel and managers in each group.

We asked participants where most of the food waste in GLC currently occurs. All groups agree that this is in the packaging and calibration phase. Interestingly the groups see different causes for this. Some think this is due to a lack of investment in machinery and the need to redesign the production process, so more internal GLC related factors. The other group indicated more external causes such as customer requirements and pressure on production costs as well as high product variability. Other causes that were mentioned were incorrect fruit quality

assessments and occasional discrepancies in product calibration criteria, losses that occur in the greenhouse, the need for better fruit selection and improved crop management.

When asked how these losses could be reduced we see that they suggest solutions in line with the indicated challenges. To counter the losses in storage, calibration and packaging participants feel that GLC needs to invest in storage and machinery across various production areas. Stricter control of temperature, humidity, and gases like ethylene during product storage in the warehouse could extend shelf life and prevent food waste. In the packaging stage, improving machinery performance, whether through better maintenance or investment in new equipment, could help reduce waste caused by suboptimal operation (e.g., incorrect weight measurements, products falling to the ground during movement, etc.). Some groups pointed out that training for personnel to correctly operate the equipment would also be needed.

Another group of reported solutions to fight food waste relate to the activities in the greenhouses. They estimate that better crop management and delivering clean produce with the right colour, size, and no pests will allow to reduce food waste. This would be achieved by planning and trained experts to provide farmers with accurate information and ensure a shared understanding. Farmers would be able to better understand the customer demands like maximal weight standards for specific countries. Some participants indicate that GLC should award penalties or rewards to farmers that respect the colour, size, cleanliness and pestfree requirements. Ideally, classifying and measuring the quality of an entire batch of product from a farmer would be beneficial to prevent FLW (Food Loss and Waste) in later stages.

Finally we asked if they feel the ZeroW solution will help them to reduce food waste at GLC. Most participants believe that the ZeroW solution would indeed provide value (aligning with the feedback from other working groups during the session) in different ways. The platform capable of measuring °Brix, firmness, colour, and identifying ugly food could have a positive impact in reducing FLW (Food Loss and Waste) during the product reception phase. This is because it would help assess the product and assign its quality, ensuring that customer specifications are met before calibration. For the second solution, which can distinguish between organic and non-organic samples, they think it would help prevent FLW at the reception stage by ensuring proper product classification, avoiding mislabelling and potential claims. Additionally, it offers the advantage of being faster than conventional analyses, which typically take 2-3 days to deliver results - reducing product shelf life. This solution would also allow for the analysis of a larger number of samples. Additionally participants think that the solution could be beneficial in the packaging phase. A second pass of the product could help ensure quality at the final stage and identify ugly food that may not have been detected the first time.

However, they also consider that technology alone - whether ZeroW or the currently implemented systems - will not be enough to improve the situation unless more efficient production processes are implemented with a comprehensive, system-wide approach.

3.6 SILL 6

The workshop took place 11/06/2025 at Aldelís (Zaragoza, Spain) and was organised by the Aldelís representatives involved in the ZeroW project supported by Asincar, based on a template developed by WP6 partners ILVO and TNO. A diverse group of Aldelís personnel, Asincar and ITA representatives attended the workshop, including 12 participants from various departments:

- Marketing and Communication
- R&D (product development and ZeroW project)
- Procurement
- Sustainability
- Quality and Food Safety
- Environmental Technician (residue management)
- Logistics
- Engineering
- Human Resources
- IT

The workshop began with a general food waste quiz to share basic insights on food loss and waste. Participants were generally aware of the issue, with most guessing that food waste levels were around 20–30%, which matched the actual figure (30%). However, they were surprised by the high percentage of food waste occurring at household level (50%), which sparked concern and discussion. Participants reflected on their own habits, noting that having children often increases household food waste, while others try to reduce waste by consuming leftovers or prioritizing food nearing expiry. The group agreed that more awareness and planning could help reduce food waste at home.

After this personal reflection, the discussion shifted to food waste in the professional context of Aldelís. Most participants felt that the company is making efforts to reduce food waste and that sustainability is embedded in its practices. However, some expressed scepticism, noting that while the strategy is clear on paper, implementation sometimes falls short. Examples of good practices included redistributing near-expiry or damaged products to employees, though not all employees collect them, and some products end up as animal by-products. The economic impact of food waste was also highlighted, with some departments viewing waste reduction more as a business opportunity than a sustainability goal.

Informing this diverse group of employees about Aldelís' efforts in the ZeroW project was valuable, as it helped align perspectives and raise awareness across departments.

After the plenary presentation, the group was split into three smaller breakout groups to discuss food waste in more detail. Each group had a mix of roles to ensure diverse input.

When asked where most food waste occurs in Aldelís, all groups identified the mince, dough, and shape steps as key points of loss. Causes included incorrect salt/additive concentrations, meat quality issues, and temperature problems during storage. One group also highlighted waste during cool storage, poultry meat preparation, and packaging, due to mislabelling and low product rotation.

To reduce these losses, participants proposed solutions aligned with the identified challenges. These included:

- Real-time monitoring and alert systems for salt concentration
- Optical sensors developed in the ZeroW project
- Improved meat quality control and supplier specifications
- Environmental Management Systems (EMS) for stock rotation
- Better packaging controls (e.g., QR codes, gas leakage detection, expiry date checks)

Participants agreed that the ZeroW solution would be highly beneficial. It targets critical steps in the production line and offers tools for real-time control, which could reduce complaints, returns, and food waste. The solution is expected to make technicians' and inspectors' jobs easier, increase sample analysis, and improve overall process control. However, participants also emphasized that technology alone is not enough. A comprehensive, system-wide approach is needed, including better planning, cross-departmental coordination, and employee engagement to truly minimize food waste.

3.7 SILL 7

In August 2025 Systemic Innovation Living Lab 7 (SILL7) contributes to the ZeroW mission by exploring how **dynamic markdown strategies** in fresh food retail can reduce food waste while sustaining retailer profitability. The Living Lab developed simulation-based pricing models grounded in operations research, examining how retailers can adjust price levels based on real-time expiry data. Capacity building in this context has focused on **strategic networking, stakeholder engagement, and follow-up research development**, laying the groundwork for long-term collaboration and innovation to further the created models.

3.7.1 ECR Retail Loss & Food Waste Seminars – Building Industry-Science Bridges

Context and Motivation

Initially, SILL7 considered capacity building via a workshop on tax incentives for food donation. However, industry feedback and internal analysis revealed that donation decisions are only marginally influenced by tax mechanisms, while dynamic pricing strategies are far more central to operational choices in retail.

Action Taken

Instead of a tax-focused workshop, SILL7 contributed to two ECR Retail Loss & Food Waste seminars (April 9 and June 11, 2025) focusing on dynamic pricing informed by product expiry data. These sessions were built around modelling insights derived from simulation and optimization studies.

The April session, hosted under the theme “*Expiry Date Visibility*”, was attended by 81 participants, predominantly from international retail and logistics sectors. Presentations focused on expiration-date-based pricing strategies and improved ordering policies using stock-age information. The methodology compared several pricing strategies - including static, last-day, and multi-day dynamic markdowns - and demonstrated a 36% reduction in waste with up to 3% increased profitability through optimal discounting models (see presentation: *Hajjema, 2025*).

Key Capacity Building Outcomes

- Raised industry awareness of modelling-based markdown strategies.
- Initiated direct knowledge exchange with multiple companies and institutions.
- Triggered collaborative outputs, including:
 - Contribution to an upcoming white paper led by GS1, directly requested following the presentation.
 - Exchange of research agendas with INESC TEC (Portugal), potentially leading to future collaboration on discounting strategies in supermarkets.

The early-stage dialogue with key stakeholders (some preferring confidentiality) is seen as a vital capacity-building outcome, aimed at producing a formal project proposal in the (near) future. It reflects the extended timeline typically needed for research-industry co-creation and sets a foundation for future systemic innovation partnerships.

3.7.2 Follow-Up Research Project SCOPE – From Dissemination to Application

Background and Objective

As a direct continuation of SILL7 research themes, the team developed and submitted a new collaborative research proposal titled SCOPE, focused on bridging gaps between surplus food availability and food bank logistics. The proposal extends the systemic insights from ZeroW, particularly around price incentives and redistribution mechanisms, into a practically embedded research trajectory with public and private actors.

Partnership and Approach

The SCOPE consortium includes:

- Voedselbanken Nederland (Dutch national food bank network)
- Dutch Date Labelling Coalition (linked to “Stichting Samen Tegen Voedselverspilling” – NGO Together Against Foodwaste)
- Two commercial partners
- Academic leadership from Wageningen University and Tilburg University

This partnership emerged from capacity-building outreach, where modelling results were shared with stakeholders and used to co-identify systemic pain points related to surplus flows and consumer communication.

Results

- The proposal was granted funding by TKI Dinalog under the PPS (Public-Private Partnership) scheme.
- Funding supports the recruitment of a PhD researcher who will co-develop interventions with partners, focusing on practical challenges in redistribution, dynamic labelling, and behavioural incentives.
- The PhD will be supervised at Wageningen University with co-supervision by Tilburg University.

This new research track strengthens the ZeroW impact pathway by translating system modelling into applied, stakeholder-driven innovation and further expanding the collaborative network of SILL7.

3.7.3 Reflections and Next Steps

The capacity building efforts in SILL7 reflect the project’s commitment to long-term stakeholder engagement, science-industry dialogue, and practical translation of systemic insights. While these activities are still in early stages, they have already:

- Enhanced visibility of dynamic pricing and markdown modelling as systemic levers in FLW reduction.
- Facilitated cross-sector collaboration, from retail and logistics to social food redistribution.

- Secured new funding and researcher capacity for post-ZeroW application and innovation.

Ongoing efforts will focus on:

- Deepening relationships initiated through the ECR platform and SCOPE.
- Co-developing practice-oriented trials of markdown strategies with retailers.
- Sharing models and training tools with additional European partners and food system actors.

3.8 SILL 8

3.8.1. CBAs relating to the challenge equipment certification

Results from desktop research: Other ways of Chemical and Mechanical Processing of Animal By-Products

The processing of animal by-products can yield valuable products for industries such as food, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and biofuels. Except for dehydration, the processing of animal by-products can rely on a combination of chemical, physical, and enzymatic processes and a variety of specialised equipment. Methods such as distillation, hydrogenation, and saponification are applied to purify, stabilise, or convert raw materials into usable outputs like soaps, lubricants, and biofuels. Physical processes, including drying and centrifugation, focus on separating solids from liquids and recovering materials such as proteins and fats. Enzymatic processing introduces biological catalysts to break down complex molecules under mild conditions, making it an eco-friendly alternative for sensitive materials.

More specifically, distillation involves heating a liquid mixture to produce vapour, which is then condensed back to liquid form, enabling the purification or isolation of specific components such as fatty acids or essential oils. Animal parts and by-products that are commonly used in various distillation processes are fat, lard, tallow, fish oil, wool grease, bones, and skin. Equipment like rotary evaporators, distillation columns, and short-path distillation units cater to diverse scales and applications, from laboratory to industrial settings. For instance, rotary evaporators have rotating flasks that increase the surface area of the liquid being evaporated (example: [Heidolph Hei-VAP Industrial Rotary Evaporator with Glassware R](#)) and vacuum distillation systems are used for distilling compounds requiring lower temperatures or separating heat-sensitive materials under reduced pressure (example: [Hei-Vac Valve Industrial](#)). Both systems are ideal for small- and medium-scale applications.

With animal by-products, distillation can be applied with the purpose of:

- **Purification:** to purify animal fats and oils by removing solvents or other impurities making it suitable for further processing into products like soap, cosmetics, or biofuels.

- **Fractionation of animal fats:** separating different lipid components into fatty acids and glycerides for specific industrial applications (cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, food additives).
- **Solvent Removal:** removing solvents used during the extraction process in the production of gelatine or collagen from animal byproducts.
- **Extraction:** extraction and concentration of essential oils from animal sources (such as musk or ambergris).
- **Concentration:** concentration of enzyme or protein extracts derived from animal tissues.

Unlike distillation, hydrogenation involves adding hydrogen to unsaturated organic compounds to stabilise fats and oils, often improving their shelf life. This reaction transforms double bonds into single bonds in unsaturated fatty acids under high pressure and temperature, typically facilitated by catalysts such as nickel or platinum. The process can be partial (resulting in trans fats for margarine production) or full (yielding completely saturated fats). Equipment like stainless steel reactors and glass-lined reactors are the most common types of reactors (example: [Pressure reactors for kilo labs and small-scale production](#)). They are durable and capable of withstanding extreme conditions like high pressure and temperature and are relatively easy to clean and maintain. Glass-lined reactors are especially valued for a non-stick that helps prevent contamination, as it is easy to clean and doesn't absorb or interact with materials from previous batches. Agitated and fixed-bed reactors enhance efficiency in mixing and large-scale production (example: [Fixed & Fluidized Bed Reactors](#)). Hydrogenation can be applied to a variety of animal by-products beyond fat, lard, oil, grease, skin and bones, including blood plasma, connective tissues and even feathers.

With animal by-products, hydrogenation can be applied with the purpose of:

- **Stabilisation:** Fish oils, which are high in polyunsaturated fatty acids, can be partially hydrogenated, which is helpful in the production of food-grade oils and dietary supplements.
- **Conversion:** Conversion of tallow and lard into more solid forms for producing margarine, shortening, and other food products.
- **Modification:** Hydrogenation can be used to modify the properties of poultry fats, making them more suitable for specific applications, such as in baked goods or processed foods.
- **Production of fat blends:** Hydrogenation can also be applied to animal fat blends derived from meat processing, stabilising them and making them suitable for various industrial applications.

Enzymatic processing uses enzymes to catalyse reactions under mild conditions without harsh chemicals. This method is employed for breaking down complex

animal by-products into simpler molecules. Animal parts and by-products that are commonly used in various enzymatic processes are proteins, fats, skins and bones. Equipment for enzymatic processing includes bioreactors and centrifuges. Bioreactors are designed to support biologically active environments for the growth of cells, tissues, or microorganisms under controlled conditions. The equipment can range from small laboratory-scale reactors to large industrial fermenters, equipped with controls for temperature, pH, and agitation, can be made of glass, stainless steel, or other materials depending on the application (example: [Sartorius Biostat® B-DCU](#)). Centrifuges use centrifugal force to separate components in a mixture based on their density. These devices are used to separate enzymes and products after the enzymatic reaction, ensuring purity and efficiency in downstream processing (example: [3-Phase Separating Decanter meatMaster CF for Animal By-Products](#), [The Flottweg Z Series High-Performance Decanter](#), [Pieralisi Decanter Centrifuge - Baby Series](#)).

With animal by-products, hydrogenation can be applied with the purpose of:

- **Hydrolysis:** Enzymes like proteases are used to break down proteins into peptides or amino acids. This process is commonly used in the production of protein hydrolysates for animal feed, food supplements, or pharmaceuticals.
- **Extraction:** Used to extract collagen from animal hides and bones, which is then purified for use in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and food products. Centrifuges can separate precipitated proteins from the liquid phase in processes like gelatine or collagen extraction.
- **Clarification:** Centrifuges can be used to clarify the fat by removing water, proteins, and other impurities.
- **Blood Separation:** Centrifuges are used to separate blood plasma from red and white blood cells, which can be used in pharmaceuticals or animal feed.

The processing of animal by-products can be tailored to industry-specific purposes (food, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals), and the required equipment ranges from small to medium and large scale. Distillation is primarily used to purify and fractionate fats and oils, remove solvents, extract essential oils, and concentrate proteins or enzymes. This process is widely used for applications such as soap production, cosmetics, and biofuels. Hydrogenation, on the other hand, stabilises or transforms unsaturated fats and oils by adding hydrogen. This method enhances shelf life, converts animal fats into solid forms for products like margarine, and modifies the properties of fats for food or industrial applications. Enzymatic processing employs enzymes to break down complex molecules in mild, eco-friendly conditions. It is particularly suited for hydrolysing proteins into peptides, extracting collagen for pharmaceuticals or cosmetics, and separating or clarifying components like blood plasma or fat.

Report on exchange meeting with Hungry Giant

During an online meeting on 15 November 2024, MC Sonae and VLTN met with representatives from Hungry Giant to discuss their mutual interest in treating food waste using technologies like the dehydrators.

Currently, MC Sonae's equipment processes 200 kg of food waste per cycle, with each cycle taking approximately 7 hours. A significant portion of this food waste includes animal by-products (ABPs), but the existing equipment is not certified to process ABPs. This presents a challenge for MC Sonae, as they seek to comply with stringent regulations while effectively managing their food waste.

Hungry Giant shared that they sell dehydrator equipment in Europe and Asia and have seen increased interest from Portugal. They agreed to provide MC Sonae with technology details on their dehydrators available in Europe. Hungry Giant emphasized the importance of pathogen clearance through pasteurization and effective recording of key data points such as cycle time, temperature, and batch details. They mentioned their ongoing work with the USDA/APHIS in the U.S. to obtain technical approval for a compliance agreement, which might be similar to what is requested in Europe.

Portugal follows the EU legislation so it was agreed that MC would forward the certification and regulatory requirements for dehydrators to Hungry Giant.

Hungry Giant also assured that their equipment meets high safety standards, offers custom engineering, and includes installation support.

Overall there is a high likelihood of follow-up meetings. Further collaboration depends on the exchange of information and Hungry Giant's ability to provide compliant dehydrators.

3.8.2. CBA relating to the challenge of waste composition implications and applications for microalgae: report on EU workshop

To support the algae sector, the EU has developed the EU Algae Initiative and the European Algae stakeholder platform EU4Algae. It has also developed synergies with other EU Commission policies and initiatives and has been working with EU national authorities to share best practices, while also funding research and innovation investments. For instance, EU4Algae maintains a research project's database with over 60 projects focused on algae-based waste treatment, highlighting the importance of algae in addressing circular bioeconomy goals.

While no algae-specific regulatory framework currently exists, algae cultivation and usage fall under various EU acts and regulations:

- 1. General Regulatory Framework for Algae:**

- a. Algae are classified as aquatic organisms under Regulation 708/2007 EU.

- b. Algae farming is governed under the aquaculture framework in Regulation 1379/2013 EU.
 - c. Products derived from algae are subject to origin declaration requirements under Regulation 1379.
 - d. Algae farming has no specific legislation but occurs in 2454 EU acts.
 - e. Algae are not (yet?) included in EU reg. 1151/2012 "Quality regimes for agricultural and food products"
 - f. Algae may be certified as organic per Regulation 848/2018
 - g. Novel food regulations apply to new food applications.
2. **When applied as fertilizers, algae may fall under the Fertilizer Regulation and/or Animal By-Product Compliance:**
- a. Algae-derived fertilizers are regulated under Reg. 1009/2019 framework, although cyanobacteria (e.g., Spirulina) are excluded as biostimulants.
 - b. For algae grown on animal-based residues, EU Regulation 1069/2009 and its implementing Regulation 142/2011 apply, outlining specific requirements for animal by-products (ABPs). These regulations govern the processing, disposal, traceability, and market standards for ABPs, which are critical for waste streams containing animal derivatives (such as that used by ZeroW SILL8).

Current regulations indicate the fragmented nature of algae legislation. Standardizing these regulatory requirements could help the sector gain better access to markets.

Ultimately, at the moment, the usage of a waste relies on two classifications and correspondent tests, which can be applied according to the Waste Framework Directive:

- **End-of-Waste (EoW) Test:** The Waste Framework Directive defines when waste ceases to be classified as waste (Article 6), provided that it meets specific environmental and health standards. For algae biomass produced from waste sources, achieving EoW status allows it to enter the market without being labeled as waste, opening doors to broader applications.
- **By-Product Test:** According to Article 5 of the directive, materials produced as a by-product, rather than waste, must meet criteria ensuring they are useful, require no additional processing, are integral to the production process, and comply with relevant regulatory standards.

Overall, legal interpretations within the EU framework are the jurisdiction of the European Court of Justice, while the European Commission can provide opinions. The workshop underscored that multiple stakeholders (e.g., ESPP) actively contribute insights to inform legislation. These contributions aim to clarify points of agreement and contention, further highlighting regulatory issues that may need resolving.

This and other relevant regulatory frameworks can be consulted here: <https://www.phosphorusplatform.eu/activities/regulatory-activities>

3.9 SILL 9

On 1st of September 2025 Systemic Innovation Living Lab 9 (SILL9) advanced the ZeroW mission by addressing household food waste through open sourcing its smart meal planning technologies. Building on its innovation research, the Living Lab shared a prototype codebase that enables recipe-product-consumer matching via an app. Capacity building has centred on open knowledge dissemination, stakeholder inspiration, and cross-sector engagement to stimulate follow-up innovation and adoption beyond the scope of ZeroW.

3.9.1 Open-Sourcing the Smart Meal Planning Prototype

Context and Motivation

Households account for over half of EU food waste, often due to poor alignment between purchasing, packaging, and dietary needs. SILL9 identified digital planning tools as a systemic lever to address this, and pursued an open innovation strategy to ensure broad accessibility and stimulate ecosystem-wide uptake.

Action Taken

In July 2025, SILL9 released its prototype app code through ZeroW's communication and dissemination channels. The code demonstrates core functionalities:

AI-driven recipe-product matching using retailer data and nutritional databases.

Household preference integration for dietary goals, allergies, and scheduling.

Waste-reduction optimisation models capable of reducing household food waste by over 90% in trials.

The release was supported by explanatory documentation and targeted dissemination to retailers, food industry partners, research institutes, and policymakers, encouraging adaptation and further development. Researchers drive a call to action to industry and institutions across Europe to take this innovation to the next steps.

Key Capacity Building Outcomes

- Raised awareness of AI-enabled tools for household-level food waste reduction.
- Lowered barriers for industry and research actors to experiment with digital systemic innovation.
- Triggered interest from retail and food service stakeholders exploring integration into loyalty apps and consumer engagement platforms.
- Strengthened EU innovation ecosystem by positioning SILL9 outputs as an open foundation for further cross-sector collaboration.

3.9.2 Reflections and Next Steps

By sharing its prototype openly, SILL9 embraced an inclusive approach to capacity building. Shifting from proprietary development to a collective innovation model. This aligns with the systemic challenges the SILL faced during the development and research, identifying a need for industrial and institutional partners that are allowed to invest (both primary SILL partners are publicly supported, and subject to strict financial regulations). This strategy empowers multiple actors to adapt, test, and embed the prototype tool in diverse food system contexts. Next steps include:

- Supporting early adopters through technical dialogue and workshops.
- Monitoring uptake and user feedback to inform future iterations and research.
- Exploring collaborative pilots that link household planning with retail stock optimisation and sustainability metrics.

SILL9's capacity building demonstrates the value of open-source systemic innovation in scaling impact beyond project boundaries, overcoming institutional and regulatory roadblocks and accelerating the transition toward zero food waste.

4. Conclusions

Capacity building activities within the ZeroW project were far from one-size-fits-all interventions. Instead, they were carefully tailored to meet the specific and diverse needs of each SILL. Recognizing the complexity and uniqueness of each systemic innovation, the project team invested significant time in understanding the operational contexts, stakeholder dynamics, and real-world constraints faced by each SILL (based on their SILL reflection). This deliberate approach ensured that every activity was not only technically relevant but also meaningful and impactful, for both the SILL teams and the external workshop participants. By asking "What's in it for them?", we ensured that engagement was purposeful and participant-centered.

These CBAs served as a vital bridge between systemic innovation and practical implementation. By addressing a wide spectrum of competencies (including but not limited to technical skills, organizational transformation, and policy engagement) the CBAs enabled SILLs to overcome bottlenecks and seize opportunities across the food supply chain. Far from being abstract or theoretical, these efforts translated directly into tangible outcomes that advanced the project's overarching goals of reducing food loss and waste (FLW) and improving resource efficiency, such as:

- Knowledge Development
 - SILL 1 - Semantic Interoperability & STH: Workshops introduced participants to semantic technologies and the Semantic Treehouse (STH), enabling better data integration and decision-making across systems.

- SILL 9 - Smart Meal Planning: Technical insights were publicly shared to engage food industry actors, allowing all to develop and adopt similar strategies.
- Addressing Policy and Regulatory Barriers
 - SILL 4 – Legal Constraints: CBAs helped navigate Flemish regulations that prohibited the transformation of withdrawn produce into long shelf-life products, unlocking new valorisation pathways.
 - SILL 8 – Microalgae Feed: Activities addressed equipment certification and legal uncertainties around converting food waste into feedstock, paving the way for regulatory acceptance.
- Connecting SILLs to Relevant Industries
 - SILL 7 - Modeling-Based Markdown Strategies: Industry awareness was raised around dynamic pricing models that reduce waste and boost profitability, particularly relevant for retail stakeholders.
 - SILL 9 - Retail & Food Service Engagement: Interest was sparked in integrating SILL 9's app into loyalty programs and consumer platforms, expanding its reach and commercial viability.
- Identification of Real-World Opportunities and Bottlenecks
 - SILL 9 – App Integration: Workshops revealed potential for embedding smart meal planning into consumer-facing apps, enhancing behavioral impact.
 - SILL 2 – Smart Packaging: Insights were gathered on consumer acceptance of smart labels, informing design and communication strategies.
 - SILL 3 – AI in Greenhouses: Feedback from large-scale farms helped refine AI-based greenhouse solutions, ensuring practical relevance and scalability.
- Operational Trust: Workshops and engagement sessions improved technology acceptance among operational staff, fostering trust and ensuring smoother implementation (SILL 5&6).

The CBAs functioned as both specialized training sessions and strategic planning workshops. They equipped each SILL with the tools to advance their innovation across their weakest systemic dimensions, whether navigating policy landscapes, market dynamics, or consumer behaviour. This dual focus ensured that innovations were not only technically sound but also socially accepted, legally compliant, and commercially viable.

In essence, the capacity building activities acted as a dynamic interface between innovation and implementation. They transformed abstract innovation potential into concrete, real-world benefits, including reducing food waste, enhancing sustainability, and driving systemic change across the European food ecosystem. Through tailored workshops, expert panels, study trips, and policy engagements, the CBAs fostered collaboration, influenced regulatory landscapes, and directly supported the adoption and scaling of ZeroW's innovations.

This comprehensive and adaptive approach has laid a strong foundation for continued impact, contributing significantly to the project's sustainability goals by turning technical advancements into lasting improvements in food waste reduction and resource efficiency.

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6. Appendix I: Overview of potential capacity building activities for all SILLs

CBA	SILL	type of scaling	challenge	CBA description	Final selection
1	1	scale up & scale out	Ensure feasibility and consistence in data collecting methods	Workshop on establishing uniform & shared procedures across food supply chain and EU regions for measurement of FLW. Together with FOLOU and Wasteless projects	
2	1	scale up & scale out	convince actors to share data	Inspirational session of successful data sharing platforms (with GS1?)	yes
3	1	scale up & scale out		Organise a workshop from D2.6: -WS 3: Value creation for end users -WS 4: BM design for end users -WS 3: Data Space BM design	
4	2	scale out	Focus on consumer acceptance and legislation related to materials and final product	Consumer panel on perception and acceptance of high-tech packaging --> workshop with packaging manufacturers	yes
5	2	scale out	Focus on consumer acceptance and legislation related to materials and final product	training for retail personel how how to explain new packaging to consumers	
6	2	scale out	Focus on consumer acceptance and legislation related to materials and final product	Information brochure on the new packaging	
7	2			Organise a workshop from D2.6: -WS 2: scoping of data space ecosystem -WS 3: Value creation for end users	
8	3	scale out	inform end users of the solution	Repeat the workshop done in 6.1 but in a region with large scale high tech farms (NL, Be)	yes
9	3	scale out	inform end users of the solution	map the differences in EU regions/farm types (Large scale greenhouses who sell directly to retail VS Many small scale outdoor producers linked to large processor)	no
10	3	scale out	inform end users of the solution	organise demonstration of the technology for farmers in a NUTS 2 region with many large scale farmers	no
11	3		Data space between the users of the technology (data owners) and the supplier of the technology/sensors. This could open up more data for the algorithm to be trained on (potentially creating a federated	Organise a workshop from D2.6: -WS 2: scoping of data space ecosystem -WS 3: Value creation for end users	no

			learning algorithm, which brings the algorithm to the data rather than the other way around).		
12	3		Creating a market place between to offer and find excess produce. Excess produce is the amount of food left after all contracts the farmer has closed, have been fulfilled.	possibly a data space workshop, could be more content focus as well	
13	4	scale up	focus on donation pathway: influence policy to make processing of donation possible	Policy Pitch & panel on June 18/19 '24 - International conference 'Towards halving food waste in Europe'	yes
14	4	scale up	focus on donation pathway: influence policy to make processing of donation possible	Flemish policy workshop	yes
15	4	scale up	focus on donation pathway: influence policy to make processing of donation possible	Demonstrate app and webservice to farmers organisations and producer organisations	
16	4		Focus on commercial activity	Brainstorm on to further develop a tool for optimal production planning (clear view on available feedstock and recipes). Linked to the market place idea CBA 12. Possibly include one of the D2.6 workshops	
17	5	scale out	improve solution acceptance from personnel	Develop a use case based on SILL 5 partners' experiences to demonstrate the amount of food waste avoided & costs saved	
18	5	scale out	improve solution acceptance from personnel	Organise workshop with tomato processors to explore opportunities of repurposing the substandard tomatoes	
19	5	scale out	improve solution acceptance from personnel	Organise workshop for GLC personnel to increase FLW awareness and see benefits of the new tool	yes
20	5		share data from GLC with Multiscan to train the algorithm	Organise a workshop from D2.6: -WS 2: scoping of data space ecosystem -WS 3: Value creation for end users	
21	6	Scale out & scale deep		Develop a use case based on SILL 6 partners' experience to demonstrate the amount of food waste avoided & costs saved. difference before and after implementation.	yes
22	6	Scale out & scale deep		Organise a workshop with other meat processing companies to better understand product requirements	

23	6	Scale out & scale deep		Organise workshop for Aldelis personnel to increase FLW awareness and see benefits of the new tool	
24	6		Data space between meet processors and the supplier of the technology/sensors. This could open up more data for the algorithm to be trained on (potentially creating a federated learning algorithm, which bring the algorithm to the data rather than the other way around).	Organise a workshop from D2.6: -WS 1: onboarding of Data space stakeholders -WS 2: scoping of data space ecosystem -WS 3: Value creation for end users	
25	7	scale up & scale out	* get demand forecasting tool and donation tool aligned	Organise workshop with retailers + policy – how to take away barriers for retailers to share real-time data to estimate food donations. Use example of Portugal (where retailers register donation to receive financial incentives)	
26	7	scale up & scale out	make transparent the donation capacity of retailers and provide incentives for retailers	mapping the different tax benefits across EU and policy workshop on the most effective ones. Organise workshop with FEBA	yes
27	7		Investigate option of data on volunteers (schedules, skills, driving licenses, etc.) which could help plan the deployment of volunteers	brainstorm on how to share data on skills and expectations of volunteers. Use this to support them better and make food banks more efficient. Organise a workshop from D2.6: -WS 1: onboarding of Data space stakeholders -WS 2: scoping of data space ecosystem -WS 3: Value creation for end users	
28	7		* sharing retailer data on expected food waste to help food banks plan in advance (links to CBA 12 and XX) * bottleneck SILL: need to make transparent the donation capacity of retailers and provide incentives for retailers	Organise a workshop from D2.6: -WS 1: onboarding of Data space stakeholders -WS 2: scoping of data space ecosystem -WS 3: Value creation for end users	
29	8	scale up	support on how to impact "laws and policy", because its easier to achieve a list of recommendations based on facts and tests but not so easy to leverage on it for them to have a wider impact	networking event where market potential and right applications are discussed	

30	8	scale up	support on how to impact "laws and policy", because its easier to achieve a list of recommendations based on facts and tests but not so easy to leverage on it for them to have a wider impact	Policy workshop	yes
31	8		Vertical supply chain to aid the planning of produce for the algae and selling the algae to another party	expand existing retail donation dashboard to motivate consumer to choose recipes that use the short in shelf life food (SILL 9), then inform foodbanks of what will be donated (SILL 7) and plan the algae production based on what could not be donated (SILL 8). Use workshop from D2.6	
32	9	scale deep		Organise a workshop (? Or some other format?) to get insight into the influence of new legislation on FLW app development?	
33	9	scale deep		Organise a workshop with consumers to understand their motivations to use the app and recipe book	
34	9			Organise a data space workshop to explore the idea to create a platform to develop and share recipes, between consumers and supermarkets	yes
35	9			expand existing retail donation dashboard to motivate consumer to choose recipes that use the short in shelf life food (SILL 9), then inform foodbanks of what will be donated (SILL 7) and plan the algae production based on what could not be donated (SILL 8). Use workshop from D2.6	

7. Appendix II: Participants to Study Visit Barcelona SILL 4

- Arnout Vercruyse, Social Welfare organisation
- Eric Demaegt, Social Entrepreneur at Harvie
- Etienne Rubens, Belgian Foodbanks Federation, SILL 4 member
- Ann Braekevelt, OVAM, SILL 4 members
- Antonio De Carluccio, Safe Food advocacy, WP 8 lead
- Renzo Akkerman, Wageningen university, SILL 7 coordinator
- Bart Van Droogenbroeck, Researcher, ILVO, SILL 4 coordinator
- Lisa Van den Bossche, Researcher, ILVO, WP 6 lead
- Alba Graells Roca, Department of agriculture, Catalonia
- Aida Marín Garcia, Department of agriculture, Catalonia

8. Appendix III: Report of site visits study trip to Barcelona

Visit 1: Indulleida

Indulleida is a company that processes fruit derivatives located in Lleida. This is a region that has a lot of fruit production (25% of the EU peaches) and the company has a close relationship with producers. Indulleida has a turnover of about €80 million per year and they process 200.000 metric tonnes of fruit. They employ about 80 FTE in production. They adapt their production schedule to the availability of the different fruit varieties throughout the year. Citrus fruit is very complementary to peaches. Indulleida is also involved in the project with the Foodbanks where surplus oranges and nectarines are processed into juice.

Fruit supply

Due to bad harvest they had to source further away than normally, but they still have enough supply. There are a lot of surplus streams available that they don't know about yet. When buying fruit they always pay the market price, no fixed prices.

Oranges are nowadays mainly (70%) sold on the fresh market and only 30% goes to industry for juice. Orange juice has become a more premium product due to the price increase of oranges. The supply has become unpredictable due to hurricanes in Florida and crop diseases.

Operating model

Indulleida's main goal is to have full production lines year round. They always start from fresh fruit (not frozen) so they depend on the seasons. They try to make use of all parts of the fruit: oil from orange peel, aroma's from evaporated water. They pasteurise the juices so that they have a long shelf life.

Another important KPI for Indulleida is the yield. When processing apples they mix different varieties to have a more stable end product. Having a stable end product

is important and challenging, the sugar content of fruit change throughout the season.

Main costs are energy and water. They are 80% self-sufficient in terms of energy.

Collaboration with food banks & managing volatility in surplus production

They manage the volatility in three ways: storage capacity, production of concentrate to save space and working in shifts. The fruit they receive from the foodbanks is processed into a juice but not bottled at Indulleida. They are paid per litre.

Visit 2 : Talkual Food

Operating model

Talkual, launched in Spain in 2020, is an innovative company dedicated to reducing food waste while supporting farmers and providing consumers with fresh, affordable produce. The company purchases fruits and vegetables that are of excellent quality but fail to meet the strict aesthetic standards of the retail market. Farmers that sell to Talkual earn more than they would by selling to industrial processors but less than in the retail market. Customers can choose between a subscription or one-time purchase of customizable boxes containing 7, 10, or 15 kilograms of produce, priced between €20 and €33, including home delivery throughout Spain. This makes the service comparable in cost to supermarket prices, with the added convenience of direct delivery. Unsold produce is donated to food banks or, if no longer fit for consumption, to animal shelters. By ensuring a year-round supply of diverse fruits and vegetables and allowing customers to personalize their orders, Talkual is reshaping consumer perceptions around food quality, promoting sustainability, and creating a fairer system for farmers and customers alike. About 85% of the Talkuals' customers have subscription and a churn rate of 10% (customers who quit). They have a turnover of €5,4 million per year and have saved 2,5 million kg of food in the past 4 years.

Visit 3: Policy workshop @ Catalan Government

Food waste policy measures

In Spain, food redistribution is supported through fiscal and legal measures aimed at reducing food waste and promoting sustainability. Food companies benefit from financial incentives, including VAT exemptions and corporate tax deductions of 40% to 50%, encouraging them to donate surplus food instead of opting for lower-priority uses like animal feed or composting. Recent legislation makes food redistribution mandatory, requiring food companies to have contracts with

redistribution organizations, with specific guidelines outlined in the law. However, this raises concerns about the capacity of these organizations to handle increased donations and the potential risk of creating waste within charities due to poor-quality donations.

Spanish law also promotes awareness and proactive measures to tackle food waste. Retail stores are encouraged to dedicate space to "ugly food" or products nearing the end of their shelf life, while companies must develop action plans to reduce food waste. These plans involve quantifying waste and collaborating with farmers and charities to raise awareness. Support for these efforts includes guides like the Catalan government's 2019 food waste prevention manual, which provides measurement methods and assistance in action plan development, with additional funding available for SMEs. While this is not yet mandatory, it is expected to become a legal requirement. AECOC (GS1 Spain) further supports these efforts through biannual conferences for retailers and suppliers and initiatives tied to the national food waste awareness day, fostering collaboration and sharing best practices.

In the context of market withdrawals under the GMO budget, redistributed food is primarily handled by food banks, with 65% distributed as fresh or raw products, 34% transformed into juice, and only 1% used as animal feed.

Organisation of withdrawals

In Catalonia there are 65 producer organizations (POs) who make use of the system of market withdrawals of surplus fruit in collaboration with DARPA, the region's agricultural ministry. POs notify DARPA three days before a withdrawal, thanks to contract-based operations rather than clock-based sales. Withdrawals are subject to strict control: at least 10% of withdrawals for free distribution are inspected, while 100% of withdrawals for other uses, such as animal feed or composting, are monitored. DARPA also oversees food bank activities, verifying compliance with commercialization rules, declared quantities, and recognized charitable organizations. To ensure proper distribution, 5% of charitable entities affiliated with each food bank are checked.

Market withdrawal payments are processed through European agricultural funds (FEAGA). POs are reimbursed for the fixed price per kilogram of fruit, transportation to food banks, and part of the logistics costs. At year-end, POs report total withdrawals and receive payments in February, which are then distributed to producers.

Surplus fruit, particularly nectarines and peaches, is often transformed into juice during the summer when peak volumes exceed the food bank's capacity for fresh

distribution. Transformation involves selecting the most cost-effective processing company, with prices around €0.30 per litre excluding packaging. Packaging and transportation to food banks are managed separately, and these processes are subject to stricter controls compared to other withdrawals.

In 2023, a total of 3,761 tons of fruit were withdrawn in Catalonia. Of this, 97% (3,638.41 tons) was allocated to free distribution, with 83% (3,140.28 tons) distributed fresh and 13% (498.13 tons) transformed into juice. The juice conversion yielded 363,640 litres, using a conversion factor of 0.73 litres per kilogram of fruit. The remaining 3% (123.28 tons) was directed to composting. DARPA's annual budget for these activities ranges from €140,000 to €180,000, ensuring effective management of surplus fruit and minimizing waste.

Folou project presentation

As part of a twinning program organised by the Folou project, efforts have been made to refine and expand the definition of food loss and waste (FLW) to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the issue. The updated definition now includes pre-harvest losses, provided the crops are ready to be harvested. Additionally, food that is rejected and returned to farms due to aesthetic standards is also considered part of FLW, addressing an often-overlooked aspect of the supply chain.

Key initiatives under this program include the development of a food loss registry specifically for farmers, enabling better tracking and quantification of FLW at the farm level. This registry aims to empower farmers with data and insights, facilitating informed decision-making to reduce waste.

Complementing this is the introduction of a sustainability tool designed to estimate FLW at the regional level. This tool provides a broader perspective on FLW trends, helping policymakers and stakeholders identify priority areas for intervention and evaluate the impact of mitigation strategies.

These measures collectively aim to create a more sustainable and efficient food system by addressing FLW comprehensively from production to distribution, with a focus on actionable data and regional cooperation.

Visit 4: Foodbanks of Barcelona

Food banks in Spain play a crucial role in redistributing food donations to those in need, with operations tailored to local circumstances such as agricultural output and the needs of immigrant populations. Donations come from a variety of sources, including producer organisations (1.5%), wholesalers (35.9%), and the food industry

(27.1%). Some of the donated produce from PO's, oranges and nectarines, is transformed into juices, and donations are often delivered in large containers such as palloxes. The quantity of food procured via ESF+ has declined a lot since the new system in Spain with vouchers. While most food is distributed through food banks, smaller donations from local supermarkets are typically directed to local charities. Finally, the Spanish foodbanks also collect food related end-of-year gifts from employers.

Spain's food banks operate in every province, with the largest located in Barcelona, which also acts as a regional coordinator. Food banks are volunteer-driven and distribute food through local organisations, which vary widely in their services, such as providing weekly food packages, warm meals, or emergency aid. These organisations adapt to the needs of their communities, and the food banks facilitate coordination among them, providing resources like fridges and cooling bags, ensuring complementary services, and hosting meetings to encourage knowledge-sharing. Most charities verify the identity of recipients before offering assistance, though social restaurants remain open to everyone.

Significant food collections include "Gran Recapte," a Christmas initiative where 2,000 pallets of food - equivalent to 1.5 million kilograms, 30% of which is milk - are donated by consumers in supermarkets <https://youtu.be/3pCQm95fRWE?si=4Unuxn3Z2ND6LUS>. This effort is supported by 250 additional volunteers, often participating as part of company team-building exercises. Other contributions come from school collections paired with educational campaigns on food waste and healthy eating, as well as initiatives to recover gifts from employers to employees at year-end.

Despite the reliance on donations, funding for food banks is variable, as they do not receive structural government support. They issue approximately 60,000 tax certificates annually to donors and rely on changing funding sources each year. Educational initiatives by food banks include the development of materials for teachers to incorporate topics like food waste and the right to food into their curricula, fostering awareness and action on these critical issues among younger generations. This is combined with a food collection action.

Visit 5: Espigoladores

Espigoladores, founded 10 years ago, is a not-for-profit foundation with 25 full-time employees working in three shifts, with one of their board members being a chef. The organisation focuses on three main goals: creating job opportunities through social integration, ensuring the right to food, and reducing food waste. Their

activities include gleaning, reprocessing food, and educational programmes such as production site visits.

Espigoladores receives funding primarily through public grants, making up 75% of their budget. These grants support efforts to integrate people into the job market and finance public tenders related to food production. They also receive annual funding from the Catalan government to organise gleaning activities, but there is no other structural government funding. Additional support comes from social investors and their own operations, which include the limited sale of products. They also produce baby food and apple compote for food banks.

For raw materials, Espigoladores sources fruit and vegetables through gleaning, which is donated to food banks with certification. They also purchase surplus from farmers for the commercial production of their own brand, 'Es Imperfect.' Farmers can bring their produce to be processed into products such as soups, pâtés, marmalades, and juices. Espigoladores assists with recipe selection, packaging, and labelling, offering this service on a break-even basis.

To manage volatility, Espigoladores plans production around the end of crop seasons. Their production site spans 1,000 square meters and strikes a balance between automation and providing meaningful job opportunities. The warehouse, which has transitioned from a horizontal to a vertical setup, helps train people to work with reachers, a common industry practice.

9. Appendix IV: Participants to Policy workshop SILL 4

- Katrien Devliegher – Flemish department of health & wellbeing - Social distribution centers – foodhub
- Arnout Vercruysse – Food Act 13/Foodsavers - deal on social distribution
- An Wauters - POD Societal reintegration (Federal government)
- Rudy Geerts - Flemish Agency of Agriculture & Fishery
- Aranka Delombaerde – Flemish Agency of Agriculture & Fishery
- Kris Roels - Flemish Agency of Agriculture & Fishery
- Ann Braeckvelt- OVAM, SILL 4 partner, OVAM is responsible for waste and food waste reduction, the Agency works together on the action plan on food loss for reduction of the food surpluses in horticulture.
- Ewoud Duttelie- City of Ostend, coordinates local food waste project, social entrepreneurship and food redistribution (W13)
- Sandra Geysels - Cooperation Hoogstraten (Producer Organisation)
- Wim Hubbrechts - Cooperation Belorta (Producer Organisation)
- Ann Decraene - VBT – technical coordinator
- Steven Desair – VWSG (organisation of Flemish cities and communities) – linking food aid to supportive measures and develop a strategy for local food redistribution organisations and food redistribution platforms.

- Rik Decadt- Cooperation REO (Producer Organisation)
- Eric Demaeght – Harvie – social entrepreneur
- Bart Van Droogenbroeck – ILVO, SILL 4 coordinator
- Isabeau Coopmans – ILVO, WP6 lead
- Lisa Van den Bossche – ILVO, WP6 lead

10. Appendix V: Report of Semantic Treehouse workshop – CBA SILL 1

Part 1: how to deploy Semantic Treehouse.

Goal of the session

This session is especially relevant for technical professionals and IT providers. We'll demonstrate how to deploy a new STH environment by following most of [the steps in our documentation pages](#). Knowledge of [Kubernetes](#) and [Helm](#) Chart is required. If you're not familiar with these tools, we might be able to show how to deploy STH locally using Docker for testing/try-out purposes.

Agenda

- 09:30 – 09:45: Welcome & introductions
- 09:45 – 10:45: STH deployment using Docker Compose demonstration– part 1
- 10:45 – 11:00: break
- 11:00 – 11:45: STH deployment using Kubernetes demonstration – part 2
- 11:45 – 12:00: Conclusion

Report

Today's workshop is about deployment, which is very technical. There are two deployment methods discussed: Docker Compose and Kubernetes setup. The Docker Compose setup is the easiest way to get started, while the Kubernetes setup is more complex but also more flexible. Four participants declared that they would work on their own computers and perform deployment using Docker Compose.

STH is a platform developed in-house by TNO, and it is open-source. The purpose of STH is to support data interoperability challenges in supply chains and other business ecosystems.

The first presentation covered the first method: Docker Compose. The overview of the architecture included a service overview and deployment steps. There are six services, see black boxes on the figure below. The deployment steps are highlighted in purple in the same figure. This was demonstrated live in the workshop and participants could follow the same steps on their own computers. This deployment method is still used by the STH team, but not so often because it is more suitable for local environments.

After STH is set up and deployed it is still empty in terms of content, which is normal because a STH can be used in various domains or sectors. How can you import the data models or ontologies that are popular in your sector? There are several ways to do this:

- Message Model: specifications of semantics and structure of data at the level of information model, this is a wizard that guides you to create a new message model
- JSON schema: Specifications of the structure and validation rules of JSON data at the level of the technical model.
- Ontology: Specifications of information at the level of conceptual model expressed in RDFS, OWL and or SHACL.
- Taxonomy: Specification of hierarchical classification of concepts.
- Technical standard: A record of specification document that is managed outside this platform and provided as a download (pdf document).
- External specification: A record of specification that is provided outside this platform, e.g. on Github, a website or other location.

These specification types will be discussed further in the second workshop.

The second deployment method discussed was Kubernetes and Helm. This method is more flexible and suitable for larger-scale deployments of STH but also more complex. If you want to get STH up and running for a larger audience in a production environment we recommend the Kubernetes method. The different services that are needed for this setup are represented in figure below. Some services are not part of Helm and you need to provide them yourself (indicated in green in the figure). None of the participants did the deployment of the SHT with Kubernetes on their own device, so the demo was shown without delay.

STH with Helm – Demo deployment

Participants indicated that they work with Docker mainly, not so much with Kubernetes but those with working knowledge of Kubernetes were confident they could follow these steps on their own at a later time.

The workshop continued with acknowledging that to bring such a platform to production requires more components in practice. How to do this depends a lot on how many users that you expect to have. There are some other components needed, for example it is crucial to have a database, but the mail service connection is optional. This information was summarized by the picture below.

TNO currently runs STH as a service to some specific sectors in The Netherlands. Together these STH instances serve hundreds of unique business users per month. These SaaS deployments are different from STH deployments for research goals in terms of expected usage and the value of the content in the platform. The power of

Kubernetes is that it allows you to implement your STH environment in all these different contexts with different usage loads and robustness requirements, this is the flexibility it offers.

The workshop ended with giving participants the option to ask questions and thanking all the trainers.

Part II how Semantic Treehouse is used.

Goal of the session

In part II we will show how to use STH to create shared common data models that ensure everyone understands data in the same way. We'll demonstrate how STH facilitates an open standardization process and how end-users (organizations that own the data) interact with the platform. Since this part will show you practically how our users use the STH as a platform to build a common language for data within their sector, it is relevant for both technical and non-technical professionals. However, some prior knowledge or experience about data syntaxes (XML, JSON), semantic web (RDF, OWL) and basic understanding of information systems architecture is preferable.

Agenda

- Welcome & introductions
- The role of TNO
- How to contribute
- Semantic interoperability? Vs Semantic standars
- Demo 1: Content
- Community
- The Dutch approach to achieve interoperability: B.O.M.O.S.
- Demo 2: STH for maintainers (SETU)
- Alternative use of STH
- Other demo's
- Conclusion

Report

TNO is an independent applied research organisation that historically does not often develop production-ready software. They often work in public-private partnerships. The work TNO does is for different sectors and so the STH team distill generic interoperability lessons from their experience in these different sectors. Their motto is that all major societal innovations require some form of data sharing.

Important to know that when you run into a problem using STH you can log an issue via GitLab. Many other users have already logged issues and TNO tries to solve them

if they are linked to a bug or missing functionalities in STH. In this way you can contribute to the further development of our platform.

In fact STH is similar to Github/GitLab, the former being a platform to collaboratively work on data models and do version control on them. The goal of STH is to help people establish semantic interoperability in their data sharing communities or supply chains. Users need to come to semantic agreements, these are then captured in a semantic model or data model. The more people use this common data model the more advantages the model brings. Increasing adoption thus becomes an important goal in itself. STH is there to create, maintain a common data model.

This is demonstrated using the example of SETU, a community of flexible staffing companies in The Netherlands. It is a very mature data model and community, meaning their maintenance process is robust and they have collaborated for a long time. The document that is standardized in the example is an electronic invoice and the electronic timecard. The semantic agreement that was developed 15 years ago was a pdf of over 120 pages defining all the information elements of an invoice, how often each element can occur on the invoice, etc. The technical mapping provides guidelines on how to implement this in your system, how to translate it to XML or JSON. Of course these documents need to be kept up to date based on feedback from the users who report bugs or missing elements.

STH replaces these pdf documents and turns it into an online repository with a tree view where you find all this information more easily and where you can directly report bugs or missing elements. Users can also see the full history of all reported bugs and missing elements. So today the semantic standard is available in a foldable table of contents, i.e. the tree view. Some elements of the tree contain sensitive personal data, this is indicated with a symbol. Some elements have reported issues, this is also indicated in the overview with a dialogue symbol, which signifies that (part of) the community is having discussions about it. This is particularly relevant for common data model maintainers. By combining all this information and interaction in the platform, you can build up a knowledge base over time.

Content and community are married here, both are very important and STH aims to provide a space to do so easy. You need the prospective users to adopt the standard and for that to happen you need to engage them and take into account their feedback. If the community is not invested in the content, the platform does not add much value. This is the core of STH.

The community is a second requirement for a successful application of STH, of a collaborative working data model. TNO has been involved in different sectors, they have common challenges: develop a standard for management and organization of open standards. Usually there is a different body created to manage the standards within a sector to make sure that the technical side of things is taken care of. Well-

known standard development organisations (SDO) can be very large (CEN, ISO) but here this acronym refers mainly to smaller sectoral organisations.

TNO noticed that these different sectors face similar challenges when implementing standards, this is why we developed STH.

Data Spaces face similar challenges when it comes to interoperability. Within a data space you can not assume there is a single community. But in general the same topics apply. Therefore STH is developed to be completely compatible with Data Spaces. It is usually referred to as a vocabulary hub in this context because that aspect of STH is mostly used for Data Spaces.

Organising semantic agreements in communities is a challenge that not only TNO faced but several organisations in different sectors. This is how B.O.M.O.S (Beheeren Ontwikkel Model voor Open Standaarden = governance and maintenance model for open standards) was developed. The document has recently been published in English, and it contains a set of best practices for setting up of semantic data standards, in particular the organisation and governance of them. There are different approaches for data sharing, you could have one large organization who enforces their model onto others. Strictly speaking, that scenario also reaches the goals of interoperability. However, B.O.M.O.S and STH are aimed at creating interoperability in an even playing field, which requires an open and collaborative approach.

Setting up a common data model requires different components, see figure below. You need operational elements to be in place as well as implementation support. But none of this will work if there is no overarching strategy that is linked to the tactics and communication elements. STH mostly supports the operations, communication and implementation support but B.O.M.O.S helps you to figure out the strategy and tactics.

As a response to a question from one of the participants, Wouter stresses that interoperability is never seamless. Unless when you have very limited variety among different organisations in terms of data and processes, but this is almost never the case. The goal of TNO is not to develop a new standard for every situation but rather reuse existing standards and build further on them as much as possible. It is important to notice that standardisation and interoperability are business challenges first and technical challenges second.

Linda Oosterheert demonstrates an application of the STH in the context of the flexible staffing industry, called SETU. They used to have codelists, contact lists, email, workgroups, maintenance requests from users and pdf documents to manage their common data model. STH tried to integrate all these elements in one solution. Interesting to know is that in the STH platform you can also see all the meetings that were held on a certain issue, the slides and notes.

The thinking behind STH comes from BOMOS, which prescribes how to build a new standard starting from an existing one. How do you get started with this? You need technical people and people who know about business processes, from different organizations. Together they need to agree on the scope of the standard they want to develop. It is important to not make it too broad, be specific. Then we can gather input on what elements need to be in the standard, translate this in a schema (XML of JSON) and then publish it so that we ensure it is an open standard! One can also add new specific messages. It looks very structured but the process is often quite chaotic in practice.

There are often different open standards available so when choosing an existing standard to start from it is important to check if the standard is being used, adopted, maintained etc. So don't reuse standards that are not good. Via the STH one can easily check if there is a living community and how they interact.

As said, the SETU is very mature example of STH use. Now how to apply this in the ZERoW context? There is a Zerow semantic treehouse environment deployed by TNO. They did the steps from day 1 of the workshop a year ago, it is available here <https://zerow.semantic-treehouse.nl/> The ZeroW ontology can now be used as a starting point for new zero waste data models. The full ZeroW ontology, built by other people in the project, is available in STH where you can select the ones that you need in your model.

In conclusion the participants are encouraged to use the existing data models and to join the community by creating issues when needed. Participants who want to try things out and need maintainer rights can contact Wouter to get them.

Part III Strategies for orchestrating data sharing ecosystems

Goal of the session

This session is aimed at decision-makers and people otherwise involved in 'orchestrating' data sharing – including from municipalities, public authorities, and businesses. We will discuss fewer technical details here. Instead we will explore the broader landscape of data sharing ecosystems and the strategic role of tools like STH. We will talk about diverse data sharing ecosystems, including data spaces and other models, based on real-world examples developed with TNO. We will distinguish these ecosystems in terms of shared business goals, levels of trust and familiarity among participants, and approaches to standardization. The point of this part is to show how different ecosystem characteristics should inform your strategy for achieving semantic interoperability and effective data sharing. Although all three parts will include interactive discussion, in part 3 we especially invite you to share your examples and discuss with us the challenges and questions you have.

Agenda

- Welcome & introductions
- Summary part I and II
- Questions
- Strategies and tactics for semantic interoperability
- STH development roadmap
- Interoperability in data spaces
- Conclusion

Report

Wouter starts with a brief recap from the first two days. Deploying STH is easy to do on your own, the webinar explains it step by step. STH is an open-source platform, it only works when you have a community. We work on common data models. These used to be very lengthy documents, STH simplified this in a tree view, with elements at the left and data on the elements at the right sides including code and comments from users.

Having a common data model is to a large extent a maintenance job, the platform needs to be managed. Many sectors are doing this often creating their own organisations to manage this collaboration e.g. GS1.

Learnings on common data models are applicable in many different sectors, we can learn from other sectors. That is why B.O.M.O.S. was launched (a document of best practice and a community, written and maintained by a community of interoperability experts from different Dutch sectors). The learnings of data model standardization are also applicable to data spaces, such as the ZeroW data space.

Today we will focus on the strategy and tactics, on the organisational part and leave the technology. We started with a tool but we ended up touching the knowledge and experience behind the tool. The main remaining challenge is not a technical

challenge, it is a business challenge. You need to build the content together but it also needs to be maintained. A useful and well maintained common data model is like a shared natural resource, a common good.

Questions from the audience

- How do you create an atmosphere of trust among partners to share data?
- How to connect with the data space connector?
- How can we build the business model?
 - There needs to be a push to start using the standard
 - How will it be funded
- Can we link our ZeroW data space with other data spaces that are not linked to FLW
- What should public authorities do to support the development a common data model? What are the resources needed? Technical and non-technical.

Strategy has mostly to do with setting up a vision and governance for a collaboration and how to finance this. Once this is in place there are many tactics the organization can employ.

We start with deciding on a suitable business model. ZeroW is now in a project phase where models have been developed and pilots executed. The question is if and how to bring this from a project form to a sustainable organisation? Can we build a structured organisation that can continue activities like the B.O.M.O.S. model? **This particular challenge of going from a project phase to an sustainable initiative phase is very common, but figuring out how to do depends a lot on the local conditions and stakeholders; this would requires a more extensive co-creation with TNO than is possible in the workshop.**

How to fund these kind of sustainable organisations? There are some examples from different sector bodies in the Netherlands.

- SETU organisation: all standards are freely available and can be applied without royalties. Their strategy is to remove barriers to adoption as much as possible.
- But then how do they finance the activities? There are 6 to 7 major flexible staffing companies that cover most of the market. These large companies benefit most from this standard and thus decided to pay in full for all activities that are needed. They also integrate their customers so that they would use the standard too. Software vendors that are asked to use the standard are also financing the activities through a smaller yearly fee.
- Sector organisation for construction (Ketenstandaard bouw & techniek): They have a pay per use approach. If you want to use the standards you need to

pay a subscription. The fees are dependent on the revenue of an organisation. Smaller companies pay a very small fee and larger companies pay more. There are about 800 members that finance the standardisation body this way, you need this large amount of users to implement this model. This model increases a bit the barrier to implement the standard due to the fee, but as a benefit it creates a direct link (sales channel so to speak) with all the users.

- You need to define 'use' in 'pay per use' and possibly engage a clearing house to manage this. But in case of Ketenstandaard they simplify it: if you implement the standard it counts as using it and thus you pay, regardless of the number of transactions.
- Transport and logistics: they use the open trip model. This started with a few market players that solved an interoperability problem, the solution was endorsed by a governmental body and is now further adopted by the market. Today there is an active open source community that maintains the standard with some management and coordination done by the sector organisation. So the organisation that needs to be funded is very small in size because the community does a lot of work themselves. There is no fee to use the standard nor to participate to the development of the standards.

Choosing the right model is one of the most challenging parts. One way to approach this, is to ask yourself if you need to found a new organisation in the first place or if you can hand-over the (ZeroW) results to some standardisation body that is already active. Do we need something new or do we find an existing organisation where you can bring in the results of a project? In the B.O.M.O.S. model the different options are described with some advantages and disadvantages of each model.

With STH we provide a decentralised approach (cf. Four Corner model) which allows to bring comfort to a group of participants to have a representative as a local central coordination point. Depending on how strong the participants are they can act on their own or join someone who is representing them. This decentralised approach allows local collaborations. Working with subscriptions is the easiest way, pay per use is complex when you scale up.

The need of the main actors in the value chain was clear in the SETU example. Is this need as clear in this ZeroW waste context. How do you trigger this need? Is it important that the need is there at the start or can this grow over time? In the SETU example the main need was to optimise the working with timesheets and invoices, from manual processing to electronic processing (EDI). This generated a lot of work and thus there was a large potential for automatizing this. This was the killer app that motivated the community to start building a common data model, and perhaps more importantly, a long term collaboration, from which later new projects came.

The SILL 1 coordinators are in the phase of generating awareness with farmer and other actors. They try to convince them to share data, that there is value for them. SILL coordinators tries to build apps (like fieldbook) for them to show them what they could do if they would share their data. In fieldbook farmers can input their operation of what they do on the field (plant protection used, etc) - things they already need to report to the government. Users are interested in data economy but they need to be convinced with instruments and apps which are not too technical and that offer them relatively fast benefits (connection to a client, an analysis that they need, a report that they are obliged to do). The more services provided in the data space the more the network will be successful.

How to onboard the early adopters? They often need to do a lot of work while the benefits will be generated only once there is a larger community using the standard. Service providers are not always motivated to onboard clients to a standard but rather onboard them to their own platform.

There are different communities using STH and we noticed that many of them struggled with managing the access to the standard, manage the subscription. TNO extended the STH functionality so that it could link with existing CRM's used by the different standard bodies to manage this from a technical perspective. That way, STH does not need to track who subscriptions, collecting the fees, this goes via the standard bodies.

Another service developed by TNO is the validation support. When organisations need to start implementing the standard, this is complex. The validation service is an integrated service to help developers check if they implemented the standard correctly or not. You can test as you are implementing it. It relates to validation & certification in the B.O.M.O.S. model. It is a service you provide to your community. Ketenstandaard also wanted certification as a next step. They wanted to show to the public who among the software providers active in their field is compliant to Ketenstandaard's standards. These companies can upload an example data message on the ketenstandaard website. The validator of STH will check in the background, a community manager double checks, and then the organisation is published on datakwaliteit.nu. After this they will receive a yearly invitation to repeat this validation.

Interoperability is also a main challenge for Data Spaces. This is linked to organisation/governance and technology. The Data Space Support Center contains a lot of knowlegde on data spaces, this is similar to B.O.M.O.S. for STH.

The classic way for system integration is where you have several applications and several interfaces via the internet. In ZeroW dataspace version one we built a connector, a software component. In the current situation this connector is distributed by many applications, such as the service catalogue. This connects to the vocabulary hub. The connection with the STH is then simply a url, it is not a technical

connection. In the service catalogue you can specify which kind of semantic model you would like to use and here we refer to the STH. In this service catalogue you can trace which services demand the use of a specific semantic model.

Low level of collaboration and trust will result in low levels of data interoperability. Especially in contexts of low familiarity between participants. The SILL partners indicate that building this community is a very new field for them but that they want to be frontrunners and take ownership on starting up a data standard community. In the case of the Transylvania Cluster the local government is also strongly involved and there is some interest from private actors but there is still a lot of work to do to make them join the platform. In Slovenia the data space is under development and compliant with EU standards. The governance model is implemented but contributors have a lot of questions regarding data ownership rights and contracts regarding the data. It is important to sort this out since we see in other sectors like Healthcare that contracts can be a blocking factors.

The platform side of STH is very well developed, but we are constantly on the lookout for innovations and integrations in the Data space world. TNO is not involved in the DS2 initiative but feel free to use our knowledge or to invite us to elaborate on the topics of Vocabulary hub and Data Spaces in general. TNO is happy to attend to a webinar or as speaker at a meeting.

11. Appendix VI: Aim, scope and agenda of CBA SILL 5 & 6

Food waste workshop for co-workers of production sites

Type of scaling: Scaling Deep = impacting cultural roots

'Why' of SILL 5/6: Make decisions quicker using new technology so that more produce becomes of value instead of waste. To achieve this, we need to establish awareness on the food waste problem and increase the understanding and acceptance of technological solutions.

Aim of the workshop:

- Assess attitudes and behaviours towards food waste
- Increase food waste awareness and knowledge among co-workers
- Engage people towards reducing food waste (both at home and at the office)
- Increase the understanding of the potential of new technologies that can support the reduction of food waste
- Create a shared common goal of fighting food waste

Who should participate

- Max 20 people
- Management responsible for setting the vision on food waste initiatives

- Co-workers that are engaged daily with food waste streams
- ZeroW Project partners to translate & summarize group discussions

Agenda

- Welcome & goal of the workshop (15 min)
- Food waste quiz (15 min)
 - Questions on food waste related to the company, the sector, Spanish consumer
- Food waste from different perspectives. What is your view on the following statements? Mental number line exercise + discussion which rules are implicit/explicit (30 min)
 - As a consumer: at home we pay attention not to waste food
 - As a company: the company takes all possible measures to reduce food waste
 - I feel like my colleagues expect me not to waste food
 - I notice that my colleagues make an effort to waste less food
 - Reducing food waste is a priority here at the workplace
- Break (30 min)
- Presentation of the ZeroW solution (20 min)
- Will the ZeroW solution help to reduce food waste in your company?
 - Plenary (10 min)
 - Mental number line exercise
 - Interview the extremes of the line & the center
 - Explain exercise and split up
 - In two groups (30 min)
 - Group 1: yes the ZeroW solution will help to reduce food waste
 - discuss how exactly this is accomplished.
 - Schematic visual of production line
 - Ask participants to indicate where in this process food waste will be reduced
 - Use arrows and other symbols to indicate the nature of this reduction: due to time saving, info sharing, instant feedback
 - Group 2: no, the ZeroW solution will not help to reduce food waste, there are other things that we could do in our company to fight food waste
 - are there other ideas you have that could help reduce food waste?
 - Schematic visual of production line

- Ask participants to indicate where in this process most food waste occurs at present
- How could we reduce food loss in these places? Using symbols to indicate time saving, info sharing, instant feedback
- Plenary feedback to the group & closing (20 min)
 - Moderators share what was said in each group
 - Thank participants

12. Appendix VII: participants to expert panel, CBA SILL 2

The expert panel took place online on 14/05/2025, 3 experts participated along with SILL2 and WP6 partners.

- Amaia Uriarte – SILL2 partner from Eroski, a leading Spanish consumer cooperative with over 1600 stores, introduced the project’s goal of improving sustainability in own-brand packaging.
- Pier Simone and Tiziana Milicia – SILL 2 partners from Novamonte, Packaging Innovation
- Caroline Van der Weerd - WP6 partner from TNO, expert on Systemic Innovation
- Ada Maria Barone (Goldsmiths, University of London), senior lecturer in marketing, shared insights on psychological mechanisms behind sustainable consumer choices and smart label perception.
- John Thøgersen (Aarhus University), professor of economic psychology, contributed expertise on sustainable consumption and packaging behaviour.
- Dr. Montse Costa Font (Scotland’s Rural College), agricultural economist, provided perspectives on food marketing, supply chain analysis, and food security.
- Jesus Palenzuela – SILL 2 coordinator from ITENE

One additional expert, Brian Rodrigo Llagas a PhD student from RMIT University: Melbourne, Australia, wanted to participate but could not due to time zone differences. He kindly provided his feedback via email, and we have included it in our summary below.